

Increasing the robustness of superstructure optimization with rigorous models via an exact reformulation

Smitha Gopinath¹ and Claire S.J. Adjiman²

¹Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, The University of Sheffield, Mappin Street, Sheffield, S1 3JD, United Kingdom

²Imperial College London, Department of Chemical Engineering, Sargent Centre for Process Systems Engineering and Institute for Molecular Science and Engineering, London, United Kingdom

April 8, 2024

Abstract

The applicability of superstructure optimization to process synthesis is often limited to simple models and flowsheets. The state operator network (SON) (Smith, E. and Pantelides, C. (1995). *Comput. & Chem. Eng.*, 19:83) overcomes some limitations via a mixer-splitter network, allowing the use of rigorous unit models. However, setting flowrates to zero for non-selected units can result in numerical issues. Here, the modified state operator network (MSON), a new exact reformulation with modified mixers and splitters, is introduced. When a unit is deselected, a fictitious, strictly positive, mixer inlet flow ensures the unit model is easily solved. A

corresponding fictitious splitter outlet counteracts this inlet, resulting in correct flowsheet behaviour. When applied to a toy flowsheet, the MSON outperforms standard formulations. When applied to the synthesis of a reactor-separator network and to a challenging counter-current column synthesis problem, the MSON offers a systematic and robust approach to superstructure optimization.

1 Introduction

Process synthesis is an important step in computational flowsheet design. It is the activity of finding:

1. the process units (from a set of allowed process units),
2. the connectivity between the selected process units, and
3. the operating conditions of each of the selected process units,

that minimize the design objective and satisfy constraints. The main approaches to process synthesis are i) decomposition-based approaches (Douglas, 1985) in which the list of flowsheet alternatives to be considered is iteratively narrowed down by using heuristics or ii) optimization-based approaches known as superstructure optimization (SO) in which all flowsheet alternatives are first embedded in a superstructure and the superstructure is then optimized. Approaches that combine heuristics and mathematical programming have also been proposed (Tula et al., 2015). The focus of this paper is on approaches to process synthesis based on superstructure optimization.

The representation of a superstructure is not unique (Kondili et al., 1993, Liñán et al., 2020, Mencarelli et al., 2020, Wu et al., 2016). In this paper, using the nomenclature given in Yeomans and Grossmann (2000b) and Smith (1996), we take as a starting point the State Operator Network (SON) (Smith, 1996, Smith and Pantelides, 1995) representation of a superstructure. In the SON paradigm, each process unit-operator (or process unit) is represented by its detailed, rigorous model. That is, each process unit is described by its

constitutive equations (including MESH equations), detailed thermodynamic model(s) as well as design, sizing and costing correlations. A network of mixers and splitters allows complete connectivity between process units. The decision variables include the discrete (binary) decisions corresponding to each conditional process unit (whether it is selected or not in the optimal flowsheet); the continuous flowrates from the outlets of process units to the inlets of process units; the (usually) continuous design variables of all the process units selected to be in the flowsheet. These design variables are the degrees of freedom for a given flowsheet topology.

The SON superstructure is appealing as the number of binary decision variables is small (equal to the number of conditional process units). It does not suffer from combinatorial explosion when the number of components considered in the flowsheet increases, unlike, say, the State Task Network (STN) representation (Kondili et al., 1993). The SON does not require the modeller to make assumptions on the performance of process units, e.g., that sharp splits are attainable in each distillation column, and is thus applicable to rigorous models. Thus, the designs obtained by the use of the SON may be realizable in practice when high-fidelity process unit models are used. A current limitation of the SON formalism introduced in Smith and Pantelides (1995) is that it is only applicable to isobaric flowsheets. Additionally, as the SON necessitates models of all units to be applicable to all components, the modelling of reactions can be more complex in the SON than with other approaches. Finally, numerical solution of the SON can be challenging as result of the use of rigorous models that are highly nonlinear and coupled.

Rigorous models for each process unit may be implemented in a chemical process simulator (PS), or a general-purpose modelling and optimization (MO) environment, or a hybrid framework in which a subset of constraints is implemented in the MO environment and the rest in the PS (Javaloyes-Antón et al., 2022). MO environments, such as GAMS (GAMS Development Corporation, 2024), AMPL (Fourer et al., 1989) and PYOMO (Bynum et al., 2021), are widely used across multiple application domains and offer interfaces to several optimization algorithms. Typically, simple, less-detailed process models have been adopted in MO environments (Dowling, 2018). PS environments, such as As-

pen Plus (AspenTech, 2015) and gPROMS (Siemens, 2024), offer built-in process libraries, initialization strategies, detailed thermodynamic models and a small choice of optimizers. Furthermore, interfacing other optimization algorithms to PS environments is not only cumbersome but also inefficient as the algebraic form of the model equations cannot be accessed.

Rigorous models usually involve a large number of nonlinear equality constraints that are highly coupled. Obtaining a point that is feasible with respect to all the constraints that describe a single process unit is, in itself, challenging. To exacerbate the issue, in the SON, the constraints of all process units are linked by the mixer-splitter network. Superstructure optimization problems, like other non-convex mixed-integer nonlinear programs (MINLPs), are prone to non-convergence in the absence of good initial guesses. In MO environments, several authors have developed process-specific initialization strategies (Barttfeld et al., 2003, Dowling and Biegler, 2015b). Global optimization of these problems is an immense challenge (Burre et al., 2023) that is outside the purview of this paper.

In this paper, we address an open challenge in the formulation and solution of superstructure optimization problems. During the optimization of a superstructure, the mass flows into any process unit that is not selected must be constrained to zero. However, the equality constraints that describe a process unit are typically well-defined only at strictly positive input flowrates. At zero flows, a number of numerical challenges arise due to either non-differentiability of the constraints or singular Jacobian matrices (Navarro-Amorós et al., 2014, Yeomans and Grossmann, 2000b). For example, the Jacobian of the mass-balance constraints can become rank deficient (Dowling and Biegler, 2015b). Additional issues are encountered for the many types of process units that require the solution of phase equilibrium (e.g., a flash unit): the constraints for these process units may be feasible and well-defined only when input flows and their intensive properties allow solutions with the desired (implied) number of phases (Cavalcanti and Barton, 2020, Gopinath et al., 2016, Skiborowski et al., 2015). Finally, mass and heat transfer correlations, as well as sizing and costing correlations, are often nonlinear functions of flowrates (such as logarithms or powers with exponents less than one) that may be non-differentiable at zero flowrates. Beyond

flowrates, constraints on other design variables can cause singularities when the process unit is not selected. For instance, consider a process unit in which the heating load is a design variable that is constrained to be zero when the process unit is not selected. In such a case, zero-valued heating loads may cause singularities in the utility-cost correlations.

To overcome the issue of singularities, several reformulations of the constraints of the process unit have been proposed. To illustrate these reformulations, let us consider a conditional toy process unit with associated binary variable z . It is described by the following model equations,

$$c = \alpha\sqrt{f^{\text{in}}} \quad (1)$$

$$f^{\text{out}} = f^{\text{in}} \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon z \leq f^{\text{in}} \leq Mz \quad (3)$$

where c is the cost of operating the unit, α , ϵ and M are constants, f^{in} is the mass flowrate into the toy unit and f^{out} is the mass flowrate from the unit. Note that in the SON, f^{in} takes the value zero when $z = 0$. Constraint (3) also forces f^{in} to be strictly positive when $z = 1$. It is easy to see that the derivative of c with respect to f^{in} is undefined at $f^{\text{in}} = 0$.

As the constraints of the process units that are not selected are redundant, the use of “big-M” (Glover, 1975) reformulations to turn on/off process unit equality constraints is customary. However, the application of the standard big-M reformulation to the equality constraints of a process unit does not necessarily address the issue of numerical singularities. The oft-used big-M reformulation of Equation (1) of the toy process unit yields

$$-M(1-z) \leq c - \alpha\sqrt{f^{\text{in}}} \leq M(1-z) \quad (4a)$$

$$-Mz \leq c \leq Mz. \quad (4b)$$

It is easy to see that derivatives of the constraints (4a) with respect to f^{in} are undefined at $f^{\text{in}} = 0$. In practice, the choice of modelling platform, optimization algorithm and even initial guess can affect the success of optimization with the big-M formulation in

cases where the constraints of a deselected conditional unit are singular. To arrive at a reformulation that is guaranteed to be differentiable and free of singularities, one may need to perform additional reformulation steps. For instance, in the toy problem, one may set $f' = f^{\text{in}} + \epsilon(1 - z)$, where ϵ is strictly positive, and substitute f' for f^{in} in Equation (4a). The use of big-M reformulation has a few other drawbacks: it entails the modification of model constraints and its use is restricted to MO environments. Moreover, optimization of big-M formulations can be numerically challenging for several reasons, e.g., due to the addition of large coefficients, the violation of constraint qualifications (Dowling and Biegler, 2015a) and the difficulty in finding valid and tight big-M parameters for all equality constraints (Trespalcios and Grossmann, 2015).

As an alternative to big-M, it is sometimes possible to use a nonlinear reformulation, although this approach is seldom used. A nonlinear reformulation of Equation (1), studied by (Burre et al., 2023)), is

$$c = z\alpha\sqrt{f^{\text{in}}}. \quad (5)$$

The derivative of c with respect to f^{in} is mathematically undefined at $f^{\text{in}} = 0$, even when this nonlinear reformulation is used. In practice, when $z = 0$, singularities may occur during the evaluation of derivatives. Thus, the success of SO with the nonlinear reformulation is based on choice of solver and optimization platform. Further, the nonlinear reformulation entails the examination and modification of a subset of model constraints.

A systematic and robust alternative is to formulate the problem as a generalized disjunctive program (GDP) (Raman and Grossmann, 1994). The toy process unit may be replaced by the following disjunction:

$$\left[\begin{array}{c} Z \\ c = \alpha\sqrt{f^{\text{in}}} \\ f^{\text{out}} = f^{\text{in}} \\ \epsilon \leq f^{\text{in}} \end{array} \right] \vee \left[\begin{array}{c} \neg Z \\ c = 0 \\ f^{\text{in}} = 0 \\ f^{\text{out}} = 0 \end{array} \right] \quad (6)$$

where Z is a logical variable associated with the decision to use the toy process unit or not.

Note that logic-based disjunction (6) may be cast as a set of mixed-integer constraints by using either the big-M reformulation which yields (4a) or the convex hull reformulation as given in Lee and Grossmann (2003). Alternatively, SO problems with nonlinear disjunctive constraints, such as Equation (6), may be solved via logic-based outer-approximation (LBOA) (Türkyay and Grossmann, 1996) which averts numerical singularities. In the LBOA algorithm, as used in the context of SO, the master problem is first initialized and thereafter primal problems (with process unit selection fixed) and master problems (the solution of which is used to select process units) are solved alternately. Model constraints corresponding to a given process unit are added to the primal problem only if that process unit is selected, resulting in a reduced primal problem. For example, in the LBOA approach, the toy process unit constraints are enforced only when the unit is selected ($Z=\text{true}$ which implies f^{in} is strictly positive). The success of this approach has been demonstrated for several problems in MO environments (Yeomans and Grossmann, 2000a,b). However, it has been observed (Caballero, 2015, Caballero et al., 2005, Navarro-Amorós et al., 2014) that simulation-based GDP may entail expensive initialization of the master problem when all the conditional units are identical, e.g., in distillation column synthesis where the conditional units are identical column trays.

In the master problem initialization step of the LBOA algorithm, linearizations of nonlinear conditional constraints across all disjunctions are added to the master problem. In the context of SO, linearizations of constraints corresponding to all the process units considered in the flowsheet are added to the master problem in the initialization step. To do this, one or more primal problems are solved (and subsequently linearized) such that all units are selected at least once. To contrast the initialization strategies in MO and PS formulations that have been proposed in the literature, we consider the example of distillation column synthesis, in which the optimal number of stages in a column is determined, via state-of-the-art MO (Yeomans and Grossmann, 2000a) and hybrid PS-based GDP (Caballero, 2015) formulations. Let N identical equilibrium stages (trays) be

allowed in each of the rectifying and stripping sections. In the MO formulation (Yeomans and Grossmann, 2000a), $2N$ binary variables are defined, each corresponding to a stage in the column. In the PS formulation (Caballero, 2015), $2N$ binary variables are defined: N of these variables correspond to rectifying column sections such that section i , $i = 1, \dots, N$ has i stages. Similarly, the next N variables denote N stripping column sections. To initialize the master problem in MO, Yeomans and Grossmann (2000a) solve only one primal problem in which all the stages in the column are selected and derive a linearization around its solution. To initialize the PS-based master problem (Caballero, 2015), at least N columns need to be optimized such that each of the rectifying and stripping sections is chosen at least once. Thus, in state-of-the-art PS-based GDP, the number of reduced primal problems to be solved during initialization may grow with the number of discrete alternatives. Further, when only one column section is to be optimized (for e.g., gas-liquid absorption columns), the initialization step entails enumeration of all discrete alternatives. In practice, Caballero (2015) observed that the solution obtained may be sensitive to the choice of primal problems around the solutions of which linearizations are accumulated in the initialization step. Lastly, the automatic generation of flowsheets with only the selected units corresponding to each reduced primal problem is non-trivial, and requires considerable interfacing between a process simulator and the LBOA algorithm (Navarro-Amorós et al., 2014).

While the reformulations considered until now (big-M, nonlinear reformulation and GDP approaches) are exact, some authors have introduced small non-zero flows to units that are not selected to avert singularities (Lee et al., 2016). However, these are neither exact nor do they guarantee feasibility of the model constraints of the process units that are not selected. In other approaches, continuous reformulations of the problem have been solved (Dowling and Biegler, 2015b, Kossack et al., 2006). The use of surrogate models has also been proposed by several authors (Bugosen et al., 2023, McBride and Sundmacher, 2019), but such approaches seldom provide optimality guarantees (Vollmer et al., 2021).

To address the challenges highlighted so far, we propose a new formulation of the superstructure optimization problem. It is based on the introduction of a modified state

operator network, MSON, such that no numerical singularities occur when a process unit is deselected. The MSON does not require the modification of process unit constraints. Furthermore, it includes a mathematically well-defined solution to the constraints of deselected units, unlike the Big-M and NL approaches. While the MSON was developed to address shortcomings in existing PS-based and hybrid optimization approaches, it may also be used in MO. A further advantage of the formulation is that it is amenable to use with black-box/grey box models of process units. The formulation relies on a simple modification of flowsheet mixers and splitters. A fictitious stream is introduced into each mixer such that the input flowrates into process units that are not selected are always strictly positive. In turn, splitters are modified so that the output flowrates that arise from the fictitious input streams are not propagated to the rest of the flowsheet. Our proposed approach provides a systematic framework to assign the states of the fictitious mixer streams such that the feasibility of the equality constraints representing deselected units is assured. The additional computational complexity arising from the MSON is small. The MSON, in its current iteration, is applicable to isobaric flowsheets at fixed pressures.

To define basic concepts, in Section 2 we formally introduce the SON and the mixer-splitter network developed in Smith and Pantelides (1995), introducing notation that can be used to construct the MSON. We next present the MSON in Section 3, based on the simple reformulation of mixers and splitters. In Section 4 we investigate the case of flowsheet synthesis and present simple case studies to illustrate the approach, including a flowsheet based on the toy process unit and a flowsheet from the literature. Next, we develop an MSON superstructure for the synthesis of a counter-current column in Section 5 and show the application of the formulation for the synthesis of an absorber for the separation of carbon dioxide from a natural gas stream.

2 State Operator Network

In this section we propose a superstructure optimization formulation that is based on the isobaric SON of Smith and Pantelides (1995). In contrast to Smith and Pantelides (1995)

Figure 1: An example SON superstructure shows 2 feeds, 2 products and 4 process units: R₁, R₂, S₁ and S₂. Each feed (product) is followed (preceded) by a source (sink). Key elements of the flowsheet are the set of units $\mathcal{U} = \{\text{Source}_1, \text{Source}_2, \text{Sink}_1, \text{Sink}_2, R_1, R_2, S_1, S_2\}$, the set of process units $\mathcal{L} = \{R_1, R_2, S_1, S_2\}$, the set of sources $\mathcal{F} = \{\text{Source}_1, \text{Source}_2\}$ and the set of sinks $\mathcal{P} = \{\text{Sink}_1, \text{Sink}_2\}$. A set of conceptual mixers (circles) and splitters (squares) connect the units and allow various flowsheet topologies including recycles (e.g., see unit S₂). Each splitter is labelled by the corresponding outlet number. R₁ and S₂ each have one mass inlet and one mass outlet. R₂ has one mass inlet and two mass outlets, whereas S₁ has 2 mass inlets and 2 mass outlets. $\mathcal{IN}_{R_1} = \{1\}$, $\mathcal{IN}_{R_2} = \{2\}$, $\mathcal{IN}_{S_1} = \{3, 4\}$, $\mathcal{IN}_{S_2} = \{5\}$, $\mathcal{IN}_{\text{Sink}_1} = \{6\}$ and $\mathcal{IN}_{\text{Sink}_2} = \{7\}$. $\mathcal{OUT}_{R_1} = \{10\}$, $\mathcal{OUT}_{R_2} = \{11, 12\}$, $\mathcal{OUT}_{S_1} = \{13, 14\}$, $\mathcal{OUT}_{S_2} = \{15\}$, $\mathcal{OUT}_{\text{Source}_1} = \{8\}$ and $\mathcal{OUT}_{\text{Source}_2} = \{9\}$.

Figure 2: Unit S_1 from Figure 1 with detailed labelling of the flows leaving the mixers and entering the splitters.

who recommend the evaluation of the optimal superstructure by enumeration of all discrete alternatives, here we state an explicit mixed-integer optimization formulation that embeds an SON. Our notation is different from that in Smith and Pantelides (1995) as we put in place the formalism that will be used in later sections to propose a modified SON and an associated superstructure optimization problem.

We begin by introducing the relevant notation. Let $\mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, m\}$ and define the index set $\mathcal{M}' \subseteq \mathcal{M}$. Consider a vector $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ where y_i , $i \in \mathcal{M}$, denotes the i th component of \mathbf{y} . Let $\mathbf{y}_{\mathcal{M}'} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{M}'|}$ be a sub-vector of \mathbf{y} defined as the vector of all the components y_i of \mathbf{y} such that $i \in \mathcal{M}'$. For a given stream defined by a subscript i and (optional) superscript j , let f_i^j denote its mass flowrate, \mathbf{q}_i^j its mass composition, T_i^j its temperature and P its pressure (the same for all streams in an isobaric flowsheet). Furthermore, let \bar{f} denote an upper bound on all flowrates. Finally, let M denote an upper bound on the magnitude of any variable ($\bar{f} \leq M$).

2.1 Preliminaries of the State Operator Network

In this section, we introduce the key sets, variables and equations in the formulation, illustrating this with the flowsheet shown in Figure 1. Consider the set \mathcal{L} of process

units allowed in the flowsheet. We use the term “process unit” to indicate both process equipment (such as an absorber, condenser) as well as any discrete subset of the process equipment (such as a stage in an absorber). Each process unit $u \in \mathcal{L}$ is described by its rigorous model equations (MESH, sizing, costing). In Figure 1, $\mathcal{L} = \{R_1, R_2, S_1, S_2\}$. \mathcal{L} is partitioned into the set of conditional (or optional) units \mathcal{T} and permanent units $\mathcal{L} \setminus \mathcal{T}$.

The *feeds* to the flowsheet are all the raw materials and utilities that enter the flowsheet. The set of *products* are all the streams, including wastes, that leave the flowsheet. Each feed (product) is modelled as a permanent process unit *source* (*sink*) with one inlet and one outlet. The sets of all sources and sinks are given by \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{P} , respectively. In Figure 1, $\mathcal{F} = \{\text{Source}_1, \text{Source}_2\}$ and $\mathcal{P} = \{\text{Sink}_1, \text{Sink}_2\}$. The set of all “flowsheet units” (including process units, sources and sinks) is given by $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{P}$.

Each flowsheet unit $u \in \mathcal{U}$ is assumed to have one or more mass inlets (from where mass enters the unit) and each flowsheet unit $u \in \mathcal{U}$ is assumed to have one or more mass outlets (from where mass leaves the unit). Each inlet (outlet) stream is assigned a unique index, shown as a subscript. The set of all mass inlet indices in $\mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{P}$ is given by \mathcal{I} . The set of all mass outlet indices in $\mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{F}$ is given by \mathcal{O} . In Figure 1, $\mathcal{I} = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$ and $\mathcal{O} = \{8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16\}$, with corresponding flowrates thus denoted by f_i^{in} , $i \in \mathcal{I}$ and f_o^{out} , $o \in \mathcal{O}$, respectively. The set of inlets corresponding to each unit $u \in \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{P}$ is described by \mathcal{IN}_u , where $\mathcal{IN}_u \subset \mathcal{I}$. Similarly, the set of outlets corresponding to each unit $u \in \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{F}$ is described by \mathcal{OUT}_u , where $\mathcal{OUT}_u \subset \mathcal{O}$. For example, process unit S_1 in Figure 1 has inlet set $\mathcal{IN}_{S_1} = \{3, 4\}$ and outlet set $\mathcal{OUT}_{S_1} = \{13, 14\}$.

To enable the representation of alternative flowsheet topologies, a “conceptual mixer” is placed before (at) each mass inlet $i \in \mathcal{IN}_u$, $u \in \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{P}$, and labelled m_i . Similarly, a “conceptual splitter” is located after (at) each outlet $o \in \mathcal{OUT}_u$, $u \in \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{F}$, and labelled s_o . These mixers and splitters are not necessarily physical process units and are not included in sets \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{U} , but they enable different flowsheet units to be connected or not.

At each inlet $i \in \mathcal{IN}_u$, mixer m_i combines $|\mathcal{M}_i|$ streams, where $\mathcal{M}_i \subseteq \mathcal{O}$ is the set of all possible outlets that may be connected (from splitters) to mixer m_i . The mixed stream leaving mixer m_i , whose state is described by the mass flowrate f_i^{in} , composition

\mathbf{q}_i^{in} , temperature T_i^{in} and pressure P , enters process unit u . Analogously, at each outlet $o \in \text{OUT}_u$ a stream whose state is described by mass flowrate f_o^{out} , composition $\mathbf{q}_o^{\text{out}}$, temperature T_o^{out} and pressure P leaves unit u . This outlet stream enters splitter s_o which produces $|\mathcal{S}_o|$ streams (with identical temperatures, pressures and compositions), where $\mathcal{S}_o \subseteq I$ is the set of all inlets that splitter s_o may be connected to (via mixers). For example, let us consider process unit S_1 in Figure 1 and Figure 2. The set of streams that enter mixer m_3 is described by $\mathcal{M}_3 = \{8, 12\}$ and those that enter mixer m_4 is given by $\mathcal{M}_4 = \{9\}$, while the set of streams that leave splitter s_{13} is $\mathcal{S}_{13} = \{7\}$ and those that leave splitter s_{14} is $\mathcal{S}_{14} = \{6, 7\}$. A stream that flows from an outlet o (via splitter s_o) to a mixer i (via mixer m_i) is labelled (o, i) , with mass flowrate $f_{o,i}$, composition $\mathbf{q}_{o,i}$, temperature $T_{o,i}$ and pressure P , e.g., see stream $f_{8,2}$ that connects splitter s_8 to mixer m_2 in Figure 1. Note that it is not possible for a splitter to be connected directly to the inlet of a process unit or for a mixer to be connected directly to the outlet of a process unit.

Once either the sets $\mathcal{M}_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}$, or the sets $\mathcal{S}_o, \forall o \in \mathcal{O}$, have been specified, the allowed connectivity of the flowsheet is fully defined. Given that each $i \in \mathcal{I}$ is associated with one flowsheet unit only (similarly for each $o \in \mathcal{O}$), the stream (o, i) corresponds to a pair of units (u, v) , such that $i \in \mathcal{IN}_v, v \in \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{P}$ and $o \in \text{OUT}_u, u \in \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{F}$. Thus, units u and v are connected, with directionality (u, v) , if there is a strictly positive flowrate between a splitter at an outlet of process unit u and a mixer at an inlet of unit v . In Figure 1, R_1 is connected to R_2 , and feeds into it, if flowrate $f_{10,2}$ is strictly positive. Similarly, R_2 is connected to R_1 , and feeds into it, if flowrate $f_{11,1}$ is strictly positive.

A binary variable z_u is associated with each process unit $u \in \mathcal{T}$ to indicate its presence in the process ($z_u = 1$) or its absence from the process ($z_u = 0$). When a unit u is not selected to be in the flowsheet, flow-validity constraints ensure that all flows directed to this unit are zero. The flow-validity constraints

$$0 \leq f_{o,i} \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_u) \quad \forall o \in \mathcal{M}_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (7)$$

thus set the flow from splitter s_o to mixer m_i to zero if mixer m_i is associated with a unit u

that is deselected. In Figure 2, when S_1 is not selected, the flow-validity constraints drive flowrates $f_{8,3}$, $f_{12,3}$ and $f_{9,4}$ to zero.

We also enforce that the inlet flowrates into the permanent process units as well as any selected process units (for which $z_u = 1$) are strictly positive.

$$\epsilon \leq f_i^{\text{in}} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{L} \setminus \mathcal{T} \quad (8)$$

$$\epsilon z_u \leq f_i^{\text{in}} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (9)$$

The following assumptions are made in deriving the SON:

1. The process is assumed to be isobaric at a constant pressure P that is fixed *a priori*.
2. All flows are assumed to be frictionless and isenthalpic.
3. Chemical reactions do not occur in mixers or splitters.
4. All units are at steady-state.
5. If the flowrates at the mass inlets are zero, then the flowrates at the outlets are zero.
6. Mixers and splitters are adiabatic.
7. The total mass flow into each sink is strictly positive.

With the assumptions that the mixers and splitters are isenthalpic and the flowsheet is isobaric, we can obtain a generic mathematical representation of the mixers and splitters. We denote the number of components in the flowsheet by K . For each mixer i , $i \in \mathcal{IN}_u$, $u \in \mathcal{U}$, we have

$$f_i^{\text{in}} = \sum_{o \in \mathcal{M}_i} f_{o,i} \quad (10a)$$

$$f_i^{\text{in}} q_{i,c}^{\text{in}} = \sum_{o \in \mathcal{M}_i} f_{o,i} q_{o,i,c} \quad \forall c \in \{1, \dots, K\} \quad (10b)$$

$$f_i^{\text{in}} h_{en}(T_i^{\text{in}}, P, \mathbf{q}_i^{\text{in}}) = \sum_{o \in \mathcal{M}_i} f_{o,i} h_{en}(T_{o,i}, P, \mathbf{q}_{o,i}) \quad (10c)$$

where $\mathbf{q}_i^{\text{in}} \in [0, 1]^K$, $\mathbf{q}_{o,i} \in [0, 1]^K$, $\forall o \in \mathcal{M}_i$ and $h_{en} : \mathbb{R}_+^{2+K} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the enthalpy (relative to a standard) per unit mass as a function of temperature T , pressure P and composition \mathbf{q} . It follows from Equations (10a) and (10b) that $\sum_{c=1}^K q_{i,c}^{\text{in}} = 1$ and it is assumed that the constraints $\sum_{c=1}^K q_{o,i,c} = 1, \forall o \in \mathcal{M}_i$, are satisfied due to mass balance equations on other units or to input specifications.

For each splitter o , $o \in \text{OUT}_u, u \in \mathcal{U}$ we have

$$f_o^{\text{out}} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_o} f_{o,i} \quad (11a)$$

$$T_o^{\text{out}} = T_{o,i} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{S}_o \quad (11b)$$

$$q_{o,c}^{\text{out}} = q_{o,i,c} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{S}_o, \quad \forall c \in \{1, \dots, K\}, \quad (11c)$$

where $\mathbf{q}_{o,i}^{\text{out}} \in [0, 1]^K$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{S}_o$ and $\mathbf{q}_o^{\text{out}} \in [0, 1]^K$.

In presenting the SON (Smith and Pantelides, 1995), we have assumed a techno-economic objective is to be optimized. The vector of continuous process variables is denoted by \mathbf{x} , $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and we define the set $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, n\}$. In addition to the variable vector \mathbf{z} that is used to select process units, the vector of discrete design variables in the flowsheet (such as feed-stage location for a distillation column) is denoted by $\mathbf{y} \in \{0, 1\}^r$ and the associated set $\mathcal{Y} = \{1, \dots, r\}$ is defined.

In constructing the SON formulation we thus consider the following types of constraints:

- Mixer splitter constraints: Equations (10) and (11) describe the mixers and splitters in the state operator network.
- Flow constraints: These include flow-validity constraints, Equation (7), as well as the non-negativity constraints on the flows at inlets of units as given by Equations (8) and (9).
- Unit-selection constraints: These constraints are used to enforce logical relationships arising from the selection of process unit (e.g, at least one reactor must be selected). This may include constraints analogous to the flow-validity constraints, Equation (7),

to assign process variables corresponding to a unit u to zero if that process unit is not selected.

- Bound constraints: Lower and upper bounds are imposed on the variable vectors \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} .
- Process unit-level constraints: For each unit u , process unit-level constraints describe the unit u via its MESH equations as well as sizing and costing correlations when applicable. Inequality constraints may also be introduced to constrain the performance of each process unit u .
- Flowsheet-level constraints: All other SON constraints are referred to as flowsheet-level constraints. These constraints usually depend either on multiple process units and/or total, flowsheet-wide quantities. For example, the total CAPEX of the process, c_{total} , is a flowsheet-wide variable defined by a flowsheet-level constraint, $c_{\text{total}} = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} c_u$, where c_u denotes the CAPEX corresponding to process unit u . Other examples of flowsheet-level constraints include constraints that are used to compute the total annualized cost (as a function of total CAPEX and OPEX) and estimate plant overheads. Flowsheet-level inequality constraints may impose performance requirements on flowsheet-level variables (e.g., a constraint on the energy demand of the entire flowsheet).

Further, we define the following index sets:

- $\mathcal{D} \subset \mathcal{N}$ is the set of indices of the components of \mathbf{x} that are the continuous design (or independent) variables in the flowsheet, i.e., $|\mathcal{D}|$ is equal to the number of continuous design degrees of freedom. Examples of design variables include the reboiler duty in a distillation column, the operating pressure of all process units and the flowrate $f_{o,i}$ between a splitter at outlet o and a mixer at inlet i ;
- $\mathcal{A}_u \subset \mathcal{D}$ describes the components of \mathbf{x} that are continuous design variables associated with process unit u only. For example, the reboiler duty of the distillation column v is indexed by \mathcal{A}_v . It follows that $\mathcal{A}_u \cap \mathcal{A}_v = \emptyset$ for any $u \in \mathcal{U}, v \in \mathcal{U}, u \neq v$;

- $\mathcal{B}_u \subseteq \mathcal{A}_u$ indexes the continuous design variables that are assigned a fixed value (assumed to be \mathbf{b}_u here) when the unit is not selected. For instance, the reboiler duty Q of the distillation column is a design variable that may be forced by a unit-selection constraint to be zero when the column is not selected. Similarly, the temperature of a utility stream at the outlet of a heat exchanger may be a design variable that is constrained to equal the inlet temperature of the stream when the heat-exchanger is deselected.
- $\mathcal{Y}_u \subset \mathcal{Y}$ indexes the discrete degrees of freedom or design variables that correspond to process unit u .

Any flow-variable $f_{o,i}$, $o \in \mathcal{O}$, $i \in \mathcal{I}$ in the mixer-splitter network does not correspond to any single unit u , as the variable denotes flows between two units, and is not represented in the set \mathcal{A}_u .

2.2 Problem statement

Given the sets of process units \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{T} , feeds \mathcal{F} and products \mathcal{P} , mixers \mathcal{I} , splitters \mathcal{O} and either set \mathcal{M}_i , $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$ or set \mathcal{S}_o , $\forall o \in \mathcal{O}$ that allows connectivity between flowsheet units \mathcal{U} , determine: i) the set of conditional units, $\mathcal{T}^* \subseteq \mathcal{T}$, to be present in the flowsheet, ii) the value of the flowrates $f_{o,i}$, $\forall o \in \mathcal{M}_i$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}$ and iii) the values of all other design variables, so that the process is feasible and the flowsheet objective is minimized.

Mathematically this SON-based optimization problem may be posed as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}} F(\mathbf{x}) \quad (12a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbf{h}_p(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (12b)$$

$$\mathbf{g}_p(\mathbf{x}) \leq \mathbf{0} \quad (12c)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{E}_u}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{0} \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U} \quad (12d)$$

$$\mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{J}_u}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \leq \mathbf{0} \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U} \setminus \mathcal{T} \quad (12e)$$

$$\mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{J}_u}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \leq M(1 - z_u) \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (12f)$$

$$\epsilon \leq f_i^{\text{in}} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{L} \setminus \mathcal{T} \quad (12g)$$

$$\epsilon z_u \leq f_i^{\text{in}} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (12h)$$

$$-Mz_u \leq \mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{B}_u} - \mathbf{b}_u \leq Mz_u \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (12i)$$

$$f_{o,i} \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_u) \quad \forall o \in \mathcal{M}_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (12j)$$

$$\text{Eqs (10)} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{P} \quad (12k)$$

$$\text{Eqs (11)} \quad \forall o \in \mathcal{OUT}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{F} \quad (12l)$$

$$Q_y \mathbf{y} + Q_z \mathbf{z} \leq \mathbf{d} \quad (12m)$$

$$\mathbf{x} \in X \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n \quad (12n)$$

$$\mathbf{y} \in \{0, 1\}^{|\mathcal{Y}|} \quad (12o)$$

$$\mathbf{z} \in \{0, 1\}^{|\mathcal{T}|} \quad (12p)$$

where $F : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denotes a flowsheet-level objective to be minimized, $\mathbf{h}_p(\mathbf{x})$ represents flowsheet-level equality constraints (e.g., a total capital cost), $\mathbf{g}_p(\mathbf{x})$ represents flowsheet-level inequality constraints (e.g., a constraint on the maximum allowable total heat duty of a flowsheet), $\mathbf{h}_u(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ and $\mathbf{g}_u(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ denote the process unit-level equality and inequality constraints for a unit u and \mathcal{E}_u and \mathcal{J}_u are the index sets for these equality and inequality constraints, respectively.

Equations (12g) and (12h) constrain the flows at the inlets of permanent and selected process units, respectively, to be strictly positive (given the constant $\epsilon > 0$) and allow

the flowrate into deselected units to be zero. A subset of the unit-specific design variables are set to constant values by Equation (12i) when the process unit is not selected. The problem solution must also respect the flow-validity constraints and equality constraints of the mixer-splitter network as represented by Equations (12j)-(12l). Equation (12m) denotes linear relationships between the discrete variables, with Q_y and Q_z constant matrices and \mathbf{d} a real vector. Note that in the SON formulation, the equality constraints (12d) corresponding to a conditional process unit u may be numerically singular when the unit is deselected. We overcome this issue through the modifications introduced in the next section.

3 The Modified State Operator Network

We propose a new and exact reformulation of the superstructure optimization problem, that is not numerically singular when a process unit is not selected. It is based on a modified state operator network. Specifically, the MSON-based formulation eliminates those singularities that are due to zero-valued mass flows into a deselected process unit. The MSON approach also avoids numerical singularities that may arise from other specifications in the model of a deselected unit, e.g, a heating load that is set to zero. The MSON-based problem may be solved via either MINLP or GDP algorithms and the MSON framework is amenable to be used in both MO and PS environments. The MSON approach is general and simple to implement in that it does not require examining or reformulating any of the equations representing the process units, irrespective of the complexity of the process unit model.

The basic idea behind the MSON approach is simple. We introduce the possibility of bypassing process units through modifications to the representation of mixers and splitters. Process units that are deselected then benefit from fictitious, non-zero, inlet and outlet flows, a feature that prevents numerical errors due to zero-flows. At the level of the flowsheet and corresponding optimization problem, these flows have no impact on the optimality or feasibility of the selected flowsheet structure, thanks to the modified mixer

and splitter models and this makes the formulation exact and robust.

We introduce the following additional sets to formulate the MSON:

- $\mathcal{W}_u \subset \mathcal{N}$ is the set of indices of the elements of \mathbf{x} that are mass flowrates f_o^{out} at the outlets $o \in \text{OUT}_u$ of process unit u .
- $\mathcal{C}_u \subset \mathcal{N} \setminus \mathcal{W}_u$ is the set of indices of the variables in \mathbf{x} that correspond only to process unit u and that appear in the objective function or at least one flowsheet-level constraint (excluding flowrates at the mass outlets). The vector $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{C}_u}$ is referred to as the output vector corresponding to unit u . The value of output variable $x_i, i \in \mathcal{C}_u$, is usually obtained by the solution of the process unit-level constraints that describe unit u . We note that \mathcal{C}_u and \mathcal{A}_u may have elements in common so that it is possible that $\mathcal{C}_u \cap \mathcal{A}_u \neq \emptyset$. Any design variable $x_i, i \in \mathcal{A}_u$, can also be an output variable if it fits the aforementioned definition. Examples of output variables include the cost c_u of unit u and the cooling duty of a reactor, Q_u . We assume here that $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{C}_u} = \mathbf{c}_u$, when the binary variable z_u equals 0. Further, $\mathcal{C}_u \cap \mathcal{C}_v = \emptyset$ for any $u \in \mathcal{U}, v \in \mathcal{U}, u \neq v$.
- $\mathcal{C} = \cup_{u \in \mathcal{T}} \mathcal{C}_u$ is the set of all unit-specific output variables.

To use the MSON, a modeller needs to have knowledge of the inputs and outputs of each conditional process unit. That is, for each conditional process unit $u \in \mathcal{T}$, the modeller needs to know i) the sets $\mathcal{IN}_u, \text{OUT}_u$ that define the mass inlets and outlets; ii) the sets \mathcal{A}_u and \mathcal{Y}_u that index the continuous and discrete design variables, respectively, for each process unit; iii) the set \mathcal{C}_u that indexes the output variables from each process unit; and iv) an assignment of the design variables, denoted by constant vectors $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{A}_u}^A$ and $\mathbf{y}_{\mathcal{Y}_u}^A$, and of the states at the inlets, denoted by $f_i^A, \mathbf{q}_i^A, T_i^A \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u$. This assignment must be feasible with respect to the equality constraints of the process unit, it must meet any user-specified lower bound on flowrates, and it must result in the expected phase behaviour. This latter requirement should be easy to satisfy and is important for the robustness and computational efficiency of the MSON-based problem solution. Only the flowsheet-wide constraints and the objective function need to be (exactly) reformulated by the modeller.

Specifically, the algebraic form of these functions does not change but they need to be expressed in terms of auxiliary variables that are introduced in the MSON.

It is important to note that the MSON framework only addresses issues related to zero-valued input flows that arise when a process unit is deselected. However, in process simulation and optimization, flows of streams within units (e.g., the vapour flowrate from a stage) can sometimes take zero value for some assignments of the design variables, usually due to a failure of the phase-equilibrium assumptions. Numerical singularities that arise in these situations are not mitigated by the use of the MSON (Raghunathan and Biegler, 2003).

3.1 Modified mixer

We now present the modified mixer at each inlet i , $\forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T}$. As shown in Figure 3b a fictitious stream is introduced into each mixer associated with a conditional unit, in addition to the streams entering a SON mixer as shown in Figure 3a. The fictitious stream is associated with a set of variables, in a similar way to all other streams, i.e., a mass flowrate f_i^M , a constant mass fraction vector \mathbf{q}_i^A , constant temperature T_i^A and constant pressure P . To avoid any issues with initialization, when the unit $u \in \mathcal{L}$ is not selected, these variables take on the assignment values. Thus, the stream at the outlet of the associated mixer i has the non-zero flowrate f_i^A , composition \mathbf{q}_i^A , and temperature T_i^A . When the unit is selected, the flowrate of the fictitious stream is forced to zero by virtue of Equation (13d) and the fictitious stream has no impact on the mixer. The corresponding

model equations are:

$$f_i^{\text{in}} = \sum_{o \in \mathcal{M}_i} f_{o,i} + f_i^{\text{M}} \quad (13a)$$

$$f_i^{\text{in}} q_{i,c}^{\text{in}} = \sum_{o \in \mathcal{M}_i} f_{o,i} q_{o,c} + f_i^{\text{M}} q_{i,c}^{\text{A}}, \quad \forall c \in \{1, \dots, K\} \quad (13b)$$

$$f_i^{\text{in}} h_{\text{en}}(T_i^{\text{in}}, P, \mathbf{q}_i^{\text{in}}) = \sum_{o \in \mathcal{M}_i} f_{o,i} h_{\text{en}}(T_{o,i}, P, \mathbf{q}_{o,i}) + f_i^{\text{M}} h_{\text{en}}(T_i^{\text{A}}, P, \mathbf{q}_i^{\text{A}}) \quad (13c)$$

$$f_i^{\text{M}} = f_i^{\text{A}}(1 - z_u) \quad (13d)$$

In addition, we set the continuous and discrete design variables corresponding to the unit u , $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{A}_u}$ and $\mathbf{y}_{\mathcal{A}_u}$, to the constant vectors $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{A}_u}^{\text{A}}$ and $\mathbf{y}_{\mathcal{A}_u}^{\text{A}}$, respectively:

$$-Mz_u \leq \mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{A}_u} - \mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{A}_u}^{\text{A}} \leq Mz_u \quad (14a)$$

$$-Mz_u \leq \mathbf{y}_{\mathcal{A}_u} - \mathbf{y}_{\mathcal{A}_u}^{\text{A}} \leq Mz_u \quad (14b)$$

where f_i^{A} , \mathbf{q}_i^{A} , T_i^{A} , $\forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u$, $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{A}_u}^{\text{A}}$ and $\mathbf{y}_{\mathcal{A}_u}^{\text{A}}$ are non-unique constants. These can be assigned any values such that the equality constraints of unit u are feasible, the desired number of phases are obtained at the solution of the unit and $f_i^{\text{A}} \geq \epsilon$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u$. If the states (flowrate, temperature and composition) at any of the inlets of unit u are design variables (that is, indexed by set \mathcal{A}_u), then the assignment of these constants must be self-consistent. Further, constraints (14a) in the MSON replace constraints (12i) in the SON and hence the independent variables of the deselected unit are assigned values in the MSON such that singularities of the equations of the unit are guaranteed not to occur. Thus, when a process unit is deselected, the feasibility of the unit model equations and the correctness of the phase behaviour are guaranteed thanks to the introduction of the modified mixer.

Figure 3: Schematic of (a) a mixer m_i as used in the SON, with its inlet and outlet streams and (b) a modified mixer \tilde{m}_i as used in the MSON, with its inlet and outlet streams. A fictitious stream f_i^M denoted by the dashed arrow (in orange) has been added to the modified mixer.

3.2 Modified splitter

The modified mixer ensures that flowrates at the inlets of conditional units are strictly non-zero but this results in non-zero values of the flowrates as well as other output variables at the outlets of units that are not selected. In addition, due to Equation (14a), all other unit-specific independent variables are assigned to non-zero values. Without modifications to the splitter, this would result in an erroneous flowsheet model. In order to correct for this, we present a modified splitter at outlet o , $\forall o \in \text{OUT}_u$, $\forall u \in \mathcal{T}$, as shown in Figure 4b in which a fictitious outlet stream f_o^S is introduced, in addition to the streams leaving the SON splitter as shown in Figure 4a. Flowrate f_i^{out} is split among $|\mathcal{S}_i|$ streams as well as a fictitious stream f_o^S . The properties of the split streams are set equal to those of the stream leaving the unit:

$$f_o^{\text{out}} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_o} f_{o,i} + f_o^S \quad (15a)$$

$$T_o^{\text{out}} = T_{o,i}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{S}_o, \quad (15b)$$

$$q_{o,c}^{\text{out}} = q_{o,i,c} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{S}_o. \quad \forall c \in \{1, \dots, K\} \quad (15c)$$

We further ensure that $f_o^S = f_o^{\text{out}}$ when $z_u = 0$ as follows:

$$f_o^{\text{out}} - f_o^S \leq \bar{f} z_u \quad (16)$$

Figure 4: Schematic of (a) a splitter s_o , as used in the SON, with associated inlet and outlet streams and (b) a modified splitter \tilde{s}_o , as used in the MSON, with associated inlet and outlet streams, including a fictitious stream f_o^S denoted by the dashed arrow (in orange).

However, when $z_u = 1$, f_o^S takes the value of zero:

$$0 \leq f_o^S \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_u) \quad (17)$$

Hence, no mass flow is propagated from process unit u to other units when $z_u = 0$. The indicator constraints (16)-(17) have been given in big-M form here, via the use of the upper bound on flowrates, \bar{f} . We re-emphasize that the big-M form is only used on the output flowrates and output variables of the splitter and the constraints of the process unit itself are unchanged. Lastly, the constraints (16)-(17) may be expressed by equivalent disjunctions, convex hull reformulations and so on.

3.3 Process-level variables

In the MSON formulation, deselected units, with their fictitious inlet and outlet streams and fixed design variables, can themselves be viewed as fictitious. The key requirement for superstructure optimization is that such units should not impact on process-level metrics and decisions. To achieve this, we define a vector \mathbf{x}^S of process variables, which replaces the vector \mathbf{x} at the flowsheet level. Specifically, consider a conditional unit $u, u \in \mathcal{T}$, that is characterized by output variables $x_i, i \in \mathcal{C}_u$. We set the value of $x_i^S, i \in \mathcal{C}_u$, to $\mathbf{c}_{\mathbf{u}i}$ when

unit u is deselected and to $x_i, i \in \mathcal{C}_u$, when it is selected. This is expressed as:

$$-M(1 - z_u) \leq x_i - x_i^S \leq M(1 - z_u) \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}_u, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (18)$$

$$-Mz_u \leq x_i^S - c_{ui} \leq Mz_u \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}_u, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (19)$$

As previously, alternatives to the big-M formulation can be used instead of Equations (18) and (19).

For all other process variables that do not arise from a variable linked to a conditional unit, i.e., $x_i, i \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \mathcal{C}$, the corresponding component of \mathbf{x}^S simply takes on the value of the process variable:

$$x_i^S = x_i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \mathcal{C}. \quad (20)$$

Since the flow into a fictional unit can no longer be equal to zero, we further replace Equation (12g) and (12h) with the following:

$$\epsilon \leq f_i^{\text{in}}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, u \in \mathcal{L}. \quad (21)$$

Finally, the objective function F and the flowsheet-level equality and inequality constraints, \mathbf{h}_p and \mathbf{g}_p respectively, are all expressed in terms of \mathbf{x}^S . We note that the only modification to the algebraic expressions for the objective and flowsheet-level constraints stems from the change of independent variables.

3.4 MSON formulation

The MSON formulation is summarized in Problem (MSON) defined by Equations (22a)-(22u):

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}^S, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}} F(\mathbf{x}^S) \quad (22a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbf{h}_p(\mathbf{x}^S) = \mathbf{0} \quad (22b)$$

$$\mathbf{g}_p(\mathbf{x}^S) \leq \mathbf{0} \quad (22c)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_{\mathcal{E}_u}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{0} \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U} \quad (22d)$$

$$\mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{J}_u}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \leq \mathbf{0} \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U} \setminus \mathcal{T} \quad (22e)$$

$$\mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{J}_u}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \leq M(1 - z_u) \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (22f)$$

$$\epsilon \leq f_i^{\text{in}} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, u \in \mathcal{L} \quad (22g)$$

$$f_{o,i} \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_u) \quad \forall o \in \mathcal{M}_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (22h)$$

$$\text{SON Mixer Eqs (10)} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in (\mathcal{L} \setminus \mathcal{T}) \cup \mathcal{P} \quad (22i)$$

$$\text{SON Splitter Eqs (11)} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{OUT}_u, \forall u \in (\mathcal{L} \setminus \mathcal{T}) \cup \mathcal{F} \quad (22j)$$

$$\text{MSON Mixer Eqs (13a) – (13c)} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (22k)$$

$$\text{MSON Mixer Conditional Eqs (13d), (14)} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (22l)$$

$$\text{MSON Splitter Eqs (15)} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{OUT}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (22m)$$

$$\text{MSON Splitter Conditional Eqs (16), (17)} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{OUT}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (22n)$$

$$\mathbf{x}^S \text{ Assignment Eqs (18), (19)} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{T} \quad (22o)$$

$$\mathbf{x}^S \text{ Assignment Eqs (20)} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \mathcal{C} \quad (22p)$$

$$Q_y \mathbf{y} + Q_z \mathbf{z} \leq \mathbf{d} \quad (22q)$$

$$\mathbf{x} \in X \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n, \mathbf{x}^S \in X \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n \quad (22r)$$

$$\mathbf{y} \in \{0, 1\}^{|\mathcal{Y}|}, \mathbf{z} \in \{0, 1\}^{|\mathcal{T}|} \quad (22s)$$

$$f_i^M \in \mathbb{R}_+ \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{IN}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (22t)$$

$$f_i^S \in \mathbb{R}_+ \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{OUT}_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (22u)$$

Note that the equality constraints that describe each process unit are not modified in this reformulation. We also note that the mixer and splitter equations for the inlets and outlets of the permanent units are unchanged from the SON formulation.

To illustrate the effect of the MSON on a process unit and flows to and from the unit, we revisit example unit S_1 in Figure 2. Figure 5(a) shows unit S_1 with modified mixers and splitters. Figure 5(b) shows the constraints on the flowrates, input variables and output variables when $z_{S_1} = 1$. In this case, at any feasible solution to the MSON, flows f_3^M and f_4^M are zero. Similarly, the fictitious flows leaving the splitters, f_{13}^S and f_{14}^S , are zero. The variables $\mathbf{x}_{C_{S_1}}^S$ are set equal to the output variables $\mathbf{x}_{C_{S_1}}$ computed for the unit. Figure 5(c) shows the constraints on the flowrates, design variables and output variables when $z_{S_1} = 0$. In this case, at any feasible solution to the MSON, flows f_3^M and f_4^M are strictly positive and equal to f_3^A and f_4^A , respectively. The variables $\mathbf{x}_{A_{S_1}}$ are set equal to $\mathbf{x}_{A_{S_1}}^A$ so that the model equations for unit S_1 are satisfied and no singularities are encountered. The fictitious flows leaving the splitters, f_{13}^S and f_{14}^S , are strictly positive. No mass is propagated to other units since flows $f_{13,7}$, $f_{14,6}$ and $f_{14,7}$ are all equal to zero. The variables $\mathbf{x}_{C_{S_1}}^S$ are set to zero.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5: (a) Unit S_1 with modified mixers and modified splitters at the inlets and outlets, respectively, shown with associated variables; (b) Unit S_1 and associated variables when $z_{S_1} = 1$; (c) Unit S_1 and associated variables when $z_{S_1} = 0$.

3.5 Implementation: The SO-PS Algorithm

The behaviour of the MSON reformulation, Problem (MSON), is investigated via an in-house C++ implementation of a logic-based variant of the outer-approximation with equality relaxation and augmented penalty (OA-ER-AP) algorithm (Kocis and Grossmann, 1987, Viswanathan and Grossmann, 1990), the SO-PS algorithm, derived by modifying the algorithm described in Gopinath et al. (2016). The use of an in-house implementation provides maximum flexibility to explore different formulations and initialization strategies.

The optimization algorithm involves the solution of a continuous primal problem and a mixed-integer master problem. The primal problem, a continuous nonlinear program (NLP) derived by fixing the discrete variables in the MINLP Problem (MSON), is implemented and solved in the modelling environment gPROMS 7.1 (Siemens, 2024). The master problem is a mixed integer linear programming problem which is solved using Gurobi 10.0.2 (Gurobi Optimization, Inc., 2024) via the C++ API.

The primal problem is solved in gPROMS using a sequential quadratic programming (SQP) solver. In the primal problem, the values of the binary variables and all other discrete variables are fixed *a priori*. The NLP solver takes a feasible path approach with respect to a subset of the SO problem constraints, namely, those equality constraints that are typically solved by the use of a variant of Newton’s method. We refer to these constraints as simulator-only constraints and they are treated implicitly by the optimizer. In our implementation the flowsheet-level equality constraints (22b), the process unit-level equality constraints (Equation(22d)), the mixer equality constraints (Equations (22i), (22k)) and the splitter equality constraints (Equations (22j), (22m)) are solved as simulator-only constraints. The remaining constraints in Problem (MSON) are referred to as optimization-only constraints. The variables chosen as degrees of freedom are declared as optimization variables \mathbf{w} and the objective function and optimization-only constraints are treated as functions of the optimization variables.

In this work, we treat conditional big-M optimization-only constraints (that are non-

linear in the optimization variables) of the following form:

$$-\mathbf{M}^u(1 - z_u) \leq \mathbf{l}^u(\mathbf{w}) \leq \mathbf{M}^u(1 - z_u) \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (23)$$

as conditional (on/off) equality constraints, where \mathbf{l}^u is a vector of v^u nonlinear conditional constraints that are true when z_u is one and M_i^u is an upper bound on the magnitude of l_i^u , $i = 1 \dots v^u$. Examples of such constraints include Equation (18), in which the output variables are implicit functions of the optimization variables. Such an on/off constraint is implemented in the primal problem with the following complementarity constraint:

$$z_u \mathbf{l}^u(\mathbf{w}) = \mathbf{0}, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (24)$$

We reiterate that the value of z_u is fixed during the solution of the primal problem, and hence no additional non-linearity is introduced into the primal problem. Based on the procedure given in Kocis and Grossmann (1987), we derive equivalent conditional inequality constraints,

$$\delta_i^{u(k)}(l_i^u(\mathbf{w}^{(k)}) + \nabla_{\mathbf{w}} l_i^u(\mathbf{w}^{(k)})[\mathbf{w} - \mathbf{w}^{(k)}]^T) \leq M_i^u(1 - z_u) \quad i \in \{1, \dots, v^u\}, u \in \mathcal{T} \quad (25)$$

where the value of $\delta_i^{u(k)}$ depends on the sign of $\lambda_i^{u(k)}$, the Lagrange multiplier (in accordance with the sign convention used in Kocis and Grossmann (1987)) associated with constraint $z_u l_i^u(\mathbf{w}) = 0$ (24) at the solution of primal problem k ; $\delta_i^{u(k)} = -1$ when $\lambda_i^{u(k)}$ is strictly negative, $\delta_i^{u(k)}$ when $\lambda_i^{u(k)}$ is strictly positive and zero otherwise; and M is a suitable upper bound on the magnitude of $\mathbf{l}(\mathbf{w})$. Treating the Big-M constraints (23) in the form (24) can avoid convergence issues in the primal problem that may otherwise arise due to the use of these linearly-dependent constraints (as the binary variables are fixed) (Dowling and Biegler, 2015a). Further, the approach also avoids linearizing both sides of the nonlinear Big-M inequalities (23) while constructing the master problem, which would result in an invalid outer-approximation of the feasible region of the constraint (see Kocis and Grossmann (1987) for more details).

As we enforce and linearize conditional constraints only when the associated binary variable is true, similar to the LBOA algorithm, the construction of the master problem in this work is also in accordance with LBOA. In the initialization phase, one or more primal problems are solved such that, across all of the initialization iterations, each process unit is selected at least once. We note that the allowable combinations of selected units are governed by the unit-selection constraints (22q) and this in turns determines the the required number of initialization iterations n_I , $1 \leq n_I \leq |\mathcal{T}|$. The initialization phase is followed by the solution phase in which the primal and master problems are solved alternately and the values of the discrete variables for each primal problem $\mathbf{z}^{(k)}$ are fixed to the solution of the previous master problem.

At the start of the LB-OA-ER-AP algorithm (logic-based OA-ER-AP), all the optimization constraints that are linear in the degrees of freedom are added to the master problem. After each solution of the primal problem, irrespective of whether the algorithm is in the initialization or solution phase, the following constraints are added to the master problem: i) if the primal problem is feasible, linearizations of the objective function and of the nonlinear optimization constraints and ii) an integer cut to prevent repetition of previously-tested binary values. Due to the inherent non-convexity of Problem (MSON), a penalty term, that allows violation of the linearizations, is added to the objective function of the master problem (Kocis and Grossmann, 1987). For all constraints we use the same value of the penalty term and set it greater than the magnitude of the largest Lagrange multiplier of all optimization-only constraints across the initialization iterations. The gPROMS gO:RUN functionality is used to solve the primal problem and access the value of the solution, optimization-only constraints and first derivatives whereas the gPROMS Foreign Object facility is used to pass the assignment of the binary variables $\mathbf{z}^{(k)}$ to the primal problem. Unlike several other simulation-based superstructure optimization studies, we do not estimate any first-order derivatives (used to construct the linearizations in the master problem) via finite differences in this work but instead use the derivatives computed by the simulator. We also note that the simulator model (or flowsheet) remains unchanged at each iteration of the algorithm, except for a change in the vector $\mathbf{z}^{(k)}$.

We also modify the heuristic stopping criteria of the LB-OA-ER-AP algorithm, akin to Bowskill et al. (2020). The algorithm converges to a solution when one of the following occurs, whichever occurs first,: i) in three consecutive iterations the primal problem is feasible and its objective function is greater than the best known upper bound; ii) the master problem is infeasible and iii) the total number of iterations exceeds 100.

We note that Problem (MSON) can also be formulated directly in gPROMS and solved using the built-in implementation of the OA-ER-AP algorithm and it can be also be formulated in other environments (e.g., GAMS (GAMS Development Corporation, 2024) or PYOMO (Bynum et al., 2021)) and solved using any of the MINLP/GDP algorithms supported.

3.6 Initialization of the simulator-only constraints with MSON

The MSON formulation as implemented with the PS-SO algorithm can be exploited to facilitate the initialization of the simulator-only constraints in the synthesis of complex flowsheets. As mentioned in the implementation section, the mixer-splitter unconditional constraints as well as the constitutive equations of all the process units are all implemented in the simulator. The feasibility of these simulator-only constraints at the initial point is essential as the primal problem is solved via a feasible path approach. However, due to the mixers and splitters which allow flow between units, the equality constraints of all the process units are coupled, and this may make initialization of the simulator-only constraints challenging. To ease initialization of the simulator-only constraints arising from Problem (MSON), here we create Problem (MSON-i), a copy of Problem (MSON) in which the following alterations are introduced to the mixer-splitter network:

- Each mixer associated with unit $u \in \mathcal{U} \setminus \mathcal{T}$ is replaced by a modified mixer. Suitable assignments to f_i^A , \mathbf{q}_i^A and T_i^A , $i \in \mathcal{IN}_u$, $u \in \mathcal{U} \setminus \mathcal{T}$ are identified.
- Each splitter associated with unit $u \in \mathcal{U} \setminus \mathcal{T}$ is replaced by a modified splitter.

The degrees of freedom of the simulator-only constraints arising from Problem (MSON-

i), which also include the flowrates between units, are next initialized in the following manner:

1. $f_{o,i} := 0$ if o is a splitter associated with any unit $u \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{L}$ and i is a mixer associated with any unit $v \in \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{P}$.
2. $f_i^M := f_i^A$ for all units $u \in \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{P}$.
3. $\mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{A}_u} := \mathbf{x}_{\mathcal{A}_u}^A$ and $\mathbf{y}_{\mathcal{A}_u} := \mathbf{y}_{\mathcal{A}_u}^A$ for all units $u \in \mathcal{L}$.

With the proposed initial setting of all the flowrates between units to zero, the feeds into the superstructure bypass the process units and flow out directly via the artificial outlet streams in the modified splitters associated with the source units. This assignment of the flowrates between units thus decouples all the units, that is, no mass flows from any unit $u \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{L}$ into any other unit $u \in \mathcal{L} \cup \mathcal{P}$. Additionally, for each unit $u \in \mathcal{L}$, the MESH equations are solved without difficulty due to the artificial mass flows from the modified mixers that are associated with the unit, as well as a consistent assignment of the degrees of freedom that correspond to the unit only. The modified mixers and splitters enable the decoupling of process units and thus result in the solution of the simulator-only constraints corresponding to Problem (MSON-i) at the initial point given above.

Further, Problem (MSON-i) is fully equivalent to Problem (MSON) when the following optimization-only constraints are added to its formulation:

- $f_i^M = 0$ if i is a mixer associated with any unit $u \in \mathcal{P} \cup \mathcal{L} \setminus \mathcal{T}$.
- $f_o^S = 0$ if o is a splitter associated with any unit $u \in \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{L} \setminus \mathcal{T}$.

The above constraints enforce that the modified mixers and splitters that are associated with permanent units behave like standard mixers and splitters as the flowrates of the fictitious streams are set to zero. This equivalent formulation of Problem (MSON) enables the systematic and robust initialization of superstructure optimization problems.

4 Flowsheet synthesis

Two flowsheet synthesis problems are considered. A synthesis problem featuring the toy unit presented in the introduction of the paper is first studied. The simplicity of the problem enables benchmarking of several problem formulation and solution approaches. We next study a flowsheet synthesis problem from the literature.

4.1 Case study 1: Toy problem

To illustrate the MSON concept and solution, we first consider a flowsheet synthesis problem featuring the toy unit that was presented in the introduction of the paper. The problem is stated as follows:

Given a feed with mass flowrate F and two identical toy units, labelled 1 and 2 and described by Equation (1), select either one or both units (the units may be connected in series or parallel), so that the sum of the costs of both units is minimized. Further, if a toy unit is selected, the mass flowrate into the unit must be greater than a positive constant ϵ .

While the SO problem considered here is trivial, we study it to illustrate the MSON formulation relative to other approaches. We test the numerical performance of different approaches to solving the toy problem, using a range of solvers in both MO and PS environments. We also note that, coincidentally, a similar problem has been recently studied in Burre et al. (2023) in the context of global optimization.

4.1.1 SON reformulation of the toy problem

We first present the SON formulation of the superstructure optimization problem for the toy flowsheet, as shown in Figure 6a. We define $\mathcal{M}_1 = \{2, 3\}$, $\mathcal{M}_2 = \{1, 3\}$ and $\mathcal{M}_3 = \{1, 2\}$ for the mixers and $\mathcal{S}_1 = \{2, 3\}$, $\mathcal{S}_2 = \{1, 3\}$ and $\mathcal{S}_3 = \{1, 2\}$ for the splitter. With the sets defined we may write Problem (SON-toy) as follows:

$$\min c_1 + c_2 \tag{26}$$

$$c_u = \alpha \sqrt{f_u^{\text{in}}} \quad \forall u \in \{1, 2\} \tag{27}$$

$$f_u^{\text{out}} = f_u^{\text{in}} \quad \forall u \in \{1, 2\} \tag{28}$$

$$F = f_{3,1} + f_{3,2} \tag{29}$$

$$f_1^{\text{in}} = f_{3,1} + f_{2,1} \tag{30}$$

$$f_2^{\text{in}} = f_{3,2} + f_{1,2} \tag{31}$$

$$f_3^{\text{in}} = f_{1,3} + f_{2,3} \tag{32}$$

$$f_1^{\text{out}} = f_{1,2} + f_{1,3} \tag{33}$$

$$f_2^{\text{out}} = f_{2,1} + f_{2,3} \tag{34}$$

$$\epsilon z_u \leq f_u^{\text{in}} \quad \forall u \in \{1, 2\} \tag{35}$$

$$f_{2,1} \leq \bar{f} z_1 \tag{36}$$

$$f_{3,1} \leq \bar{f} z_1 \tag{37}$$

$$f_{1,2} \leq \bar{f} z_2 \tag{38}$$

$$f_{3,2} \leq \bar{f} z_2 \tag{39}$$

$$z_1 + z_2 \geq 1 \tag{40}$$

We replace Equation (27) with Equation (41) to obtain Problem (BigM-toy):

$$c_u \geq \alpha \sqrt{f_u^{\text{in}}} \quad \forall u \in \{1, 2\} \tag{41}$$

We replace Equation (27) with Equation (42) to obtain Problem (NL-toy):

$$c_u = z_u \alpha \sqrt{f_u^{\text{in}}} \quad \forall u \in \{1, 2\} \tag{42}$$

Figure 6: (a) Unit selection problem for case study 1 – SON representation; (b) Unit selection problem for case study 1 – MSON representation.

4.1.2 MSON reformulation of the toy problem

We construct the MSON reformulation of the toy problem to yield Problem (MSON-toy), which is represented in Figure 6b. To do so we note that $\mathcal{C}_1 = \{1\}$ (corresponding to variable c_1) and $\mathcal{C}_2 = \{2\}$ (corresponding to variable c_2). We introduce process-level variables c_u^S and f_u^S , $u \in \{1, 2\}$. Only one of the two Big-M inequalities in Equation (18) is used here to arrive at Equation (55). Combining Equation (55) with the objective function is equivalent to including both the inequalities in (18). Problem (MSON-toy) is thus given

by:

$$\min c_1^S + c_2^S \tag{43}$$

$$c_u = \alpha \sqrt{f_u^{\text{in}}} \quad \forall u \in \{1, 2\} \tag{44}$$

$$f_u^{\text{out}} = f_u^{\text{in}} \quad \forall u \in \{1, 2\} \tag{45}$$

$$F = f_{3,1} + f_{3,2} \tag{46}$$

$$f_1^{\text{in}} = f_{3,1} + f_{2,1} + f_1^{\text{M}} \tag{47}$$

$$f_2^{\text{in}} = f_{3,2} + f_{1,2} + f_2^{\text{M}} \tag{48}$$

$$f_u^{\text{M}} = f_u^{\text{A}}(1 - z_u) \quad \forall u \in \{1, 2\} \tag{49}$$

$$f_3^{\text{in}} = f_{1,3} + f_{2,3} \tag{50}$$

$$f_1^{\text{out}} = f_{1,2} + f_{1,3} + f_1^{\text{S}} \tag{51}$$

$$f_2^{\text{out}} = f_{2,1} + f_{2,3} + f_2^{\text{S}} \tag{52}$$

$$f_i^{\text{out}} - f_u^{\text{S}} \leq \bar{f} z_u \quad \forall u \in \{1, 2\} \tag{53}$$

$$f_u^{\text{S}} \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_u) \quad \forall u \in \{1, 2\} \tag{54}$$

$$c_u - c_u^{\text{S}} \leq \bar{c}(1 - z_u) \quad \forall u \in \{1, 2\} \tag{55}$$

$$\epsilon \leq f_u^{\text{in}} \quad \forall u \in \{1, 2\} \tag{56}$$

$$f_{2,1} \leq \bar{f} z_1 \tag{57}$$

$$f_{3,1} \leq \bar{f} z_1 \tag{58}$$

$$f_{1,2} \leq \bar{f} z_2 \tag{59}$$

$$f_{3,2} \leq \bar{f} z_2 \tag{60}$$

$$z_1 + z_2 \geq 1 \tag{61}$$

where \bar{c} is an upper-bound on cost.

4.1.3 Numerical experiments on case study 1

To investigate numerical performance, we conduct numerical experiments in the gPROMS PS environment and the GAMS MO environment.

We implement and solve Problems (SON-toy), (MSON-toy), (BigM-toy) and (NL-toy) as follows:

1. formulate the MINLP in GAMS and solve it with all available local MINLP solvers, namely ALPHA ECP (denoted here as α ECP) (Lastusilta et al., 2009), DICOPT (Kocis and Grossmann, 1989), KNITRO (Byrd et al., 2006), sBB (ARKI Consulting & Development A/S, 2024b), SHOT (Kronqvist et al., 2015), and XPRESS (FICO, 2024). All solver parameters and initial guesses are set to default values.
2. formulate the MINLP in gPROMS and solve it using the native OA/ER/AP (Viswanathan and Grossmann, 1990) algorithm in gPROMS. In gPROMS, initial guesses for the degrees of freedom of a problem are a requisite and, thus, we test the following two sets of intuitive initial guesses:
 - IG-1: Both binary variables are 1 and all other degrees of freedom are set at the midpoints of their intervals.
 - IG-2: All variables are assigned their respective values at the globally optimal solution of the respective problems. The optimal solution, in which only one of the binary variables takes the value 1, is easy to arrive at.

In Table 1, under OA-1 and OA-2, we show the results from gPROMS with initial guesses IG-1 and IG-2, respectively. All continuous variables are bounded by 0 and 1 in all problems with the exception of f_1^{in} and f_2^{in} in Problem (MSON-toy) whose lower bound is set as ϵ .

Several MINLP algorithms (such as outer approximation and generalized Benders decomposition) entail the solution of primal problems in which the discrete variables are fixed to yield nonlinear programming problems. To further illustrate the numerical issues that

may arise due to singularities when a process unit is deselected, we study the numerical performance of the primal problems that arise in the solution of the toy problem. We consider two primal problems: i) Primal-11 in which both units are selected ($z_1 = 1$ and $z_2 = 1$) and ii) Primal-10 in which only unit A is selected ($z_1 = 1$ and $z_2 = 0$). (Primal-01 in which only unit B is selected is symmetric to Primal-10 as the two units are identical).

We implement and solve Primal-11 and Primal-10 that arise in the solution of problems (SON-toy), (MSON-toy), (BigM-toy) and (NL-toy) as follows:

1. formulate the NLPs in GAMS and solve them with all available local NLP solvers, namely CONOPT (ARKI Consulting & Development A/S, 2024a), SNOPT (Gill et al., 2005), IPOPT (Wächter and Biegler, 2005), KNITRO (Byrd et al., 2006), MINOS (Murtagh et al., 2002) and XPRESS (FICO, 2024). All solver parameters and initial guesses are set to default values.
2. formulate the NLPs in gPROMS and solve them using the NLPSQP solver. As NLPSQP requires initial guesses to be supplied, we initialize the continuous variables in these problems with their respective values in sets IG-1 and IG-2.

4.1.4 Results for the toy problem

In Table 1 we show the results of solving MINLP Problems (MSON-toy), (SON-toy), (BigM-toy) and (NL-toy) in GAMS and gPROMS. The results indicate that the formulation, solver choice and initial guess can impact convergence of the toy flowsheet. We test the performance of each formulation with 6 solvers in GAMS and 2 initial guesses in gPROMS resulting in a total of 8 tests for each problem formulation. Problem (BigM-toy) is the worst-performing formulation as failure to converge to a solution is observed in 4 out of the 8 tests. For Problem (SON-toy), failure to converge to a solution at all is seen in 1 out of the 8 tests. For both Problems (MSON-toy) and (NL-toy), convergence to a solution is obtained across all 8 tests. However, for Problem (NL-toy), convergence to a solution is not achieved in gPROMS when the binary variable post multiplies the cost function and the initial guess is at the problem solution, due to a failure to evaluate derivatives.

	GAMS						gPROMS	
	α ECP	DICOPT	KNITRO	SBB	SHOT	XPRESS	OA-1	OA-2
MSON-toy	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SON-toy	✓*	✓	✓	✓*	✓	✓†	✓*	✗†
BigM-toy	✓*	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗†	✗†
NL-toy	✓*	✓	✓*	✓	✓	✓†	✓	✓‡

Table 1: Results of Toy problem MINLP

✓: Converges to a locally optimal and/or feasible solution

✗: Does not converge to a solution

†: Function/derivative evaluation errors reported

*: Identifies sub-optimal solution in which both binaries are equal to 1

‡: Fails to converge due to function/derivative evaluation error when the binary variable post-multiplies the cost function in Equation (42), i.e. when $c = \alpha\sqrt{f}z$.

This indicates that the use of the nonlinear formulation does not guarantee removal of numerical singularities. Function or derivative evaluation errors are reported in a total of 5 of the total 32 tests. In our tests some MINLP solvers, for example, XPRESS in Table 1, converge to a solution even when function or derivative evaluation errors are reported.

In this study, we use only local optimization techniques that are not guaranteed to converge to the global minimum of the problem. As solving Problems (BigM-toy), (MSON-toy) and (NL-toy) results in local (not global) solutions in which both units are selected in 6 out of the 24 tests, some problem failures due to numerical singularities that arise from deselection of a toy unit may have been averted. In all 8 tests, at the solution of Problem (MSON-toy) only one unit is selected illustrating that numerical singularities are eliminated by the use of the formulation. Lastly, we test Problem (MSON-toy) using the SO-PS algorithm. The results obtained from the SO-PS algorithm, the OA/ER/AP algorithm in gPROMS and the GAMS solvers are all identical.

In Table 2 we show the results of solving Primal-11 and Primal-10 derived from Problems (MSON-toy), (SON-toy), (BigM-toy) and (NL-toy) in GAMS and gPROMS. We again test the performance of each formulation with 6 solvers in GAMS and 2 initial guesses in gPROMS resulting in a total of 8 tests for each primal problem arising from each problem formulation. We find that for Primal-11, convergence to a solution is achieved for all prob-

lem formulations for all solvers in GAMS (with default initial guesses) and in gPROMS with initial guess IG-1. With IG-2, convergence to a solution is only achieved for the formulation that corresponds to the MSON formulation. We also note that the solver IPOPT converges to a solution for the toy flowsheet despite Jacobian evaluation errors at the solver-generated initial point for Problems (SON), (BigM-toy) and (NL-toy).

For Primal-10, on the other hand, the solvers fail to converge to a solution in 28% of the 32 tests, illustrating the numerical issues that can arise when process units are deselected even in simple flowsheet synthesis problems. Function or derivative evaluation errors are reported by the solvers in 34% of the total 32 tests in which unit B is deselected as shown in Table 2. Problem (SON-toy) is the worst-performing formulation because the solution of Primal-10 results in a failure to converge in 5 out of the 8 tests. Similarly, the solution of the instances of Primal-10 that arise from Problem (BigM-toy) results in a convergence failure in 50% of the tests. Primal-10 problems derived from Problems (MSON-toy) and (NL-toy) are solved successfully across all of the 8 tests, indicating that both these formulations are promising. We note that in gPROMS with IG-2, the solver fails to converge to a solution of Primal-10 as derived from Problem (NL-toy) when the binary variable post-multiplies the cost function due to an undefined derivative. In GAMS with default initial guesses, convergence across the tested solvers is not related to the order of multiplication of the binary variable and the cost function, demonstrating that the successful performance of the nonlinear reformulation may depend on the modelling platform, and specifically the routine used to evaluate derivatives.

The results in Tables 1 and 2 illustrate that commonly used literature formulations such as Big-M and SON can be prone to non-convergence even on simple flowsheets. The results also indicate that for both the full process synthesis MINLP and the primal NLPs, the reformulation offered into the MSON is robust and removes numerical singularities due to process unit deselection. Additionally, in the MSON formulation, unlike Problem (NL-toy), simulator-only constraints do not have to be modified. This is especially advantageous as the number of such constraints tends to be large.

Table 2: Results of the primal problems for case study 1 with different fixed values of the binary variables ($z_A = z_B = 1$ for Primal-11 and $z_A = 1, z_B = 0$ for Primal-10). The MINLP formulation from which the primal problem is derived is indicated in column MINLP. Each subsequent column corresponds to a different solver (for GAMS) or initial point (for gPROMS). The symbols indicate the following: ✓: Converges to a locally optimal solution; ✗: Does not converge to a locally optimal solution; †: Function/derivative evaluation errors reported; ‡: Fails to converges due to function/derivative evaluation error when the binary variable post multiplies the cost function, i.e., when $c = \alpha\sqrt{f}z$, but succeeds when $c = z\alpha\sqrt{f}$

Primal problem	MINLP formulation	GAMS solver								gPROMS initial point	
		CONOPT	SNOPT	IPOPT	KNITRO	MINOS	XPRESS	IG-1	IG-2		
Primal-11	(MSON-toy)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	(SON-toy)	✓	✓	✓†	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗†
	(BigM-toy)	✓	✓	✓†	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗†
	(NL-toy)	✓	✓	✓†	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗†
Primal-10	(MSON-toy)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	(SON-toy)	✓	✓	✗†	✗†	✗†	✓	✓	✓	✗†	✗†
	(BigM-toy)	✓	✓	✓†	✗†	✗†	✓	✓	✓	✗†	✗†
	(NL-toy)	✓	✓	✓†	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓‡

Figure 7: SON representation of the flowsheet synthesis problem in case study 2

4.2 Case study 2: Reactor-separator network

To illustrate the MSON approach on a more challenging problem, we present its application to a reactor-separator network synthesis case study taken from Trespalacios and Grossmann (2014). The GDP formulation of the flowsheet synthesis problem as well as the Big-M and convex hull MINLP formulations of the problem are given in Trespalacios and Grossmann (2014), whereas the nonlinear MINLP formulation is given in Burre et al. (2023).

4.2.1 Problem statement

Consider a mixture with molar flowrate f_F , that may flow into up to three reactors: R_1 , R_2 and R_3 . When reactor R_3 is chosen, one of the two separators S_1 and S_2 must be selected. All streams that exit the units R_1 , R_2 , S_1 and S_2 are combined (via a mixer) to yield the product stream with molar flowrate f_P . The flowsheet superstructure is shown in Figure 7.

Each unit $u \in \mathcal{T}$, where $\mathcal{T} = \{R_1, R_2, R_3, S_1, S_2\}$, is modelled by the following equations.

$$f_u^{\text{out}} = \xi_u f_u^{\text{in}}, \quad (62)$$

$$c_u = \begin{cases} \mu_u f_u^{\text{in} \nu_u} & \text{if } u \text{ is a reactor} \\ \mu_u & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (63)$$

Table 3: Constants for case study 2

Unit u	ξ_u	μ_u	ν_u
R ₁	0.7	0.9	0.5
R ₂	0.8	0.8	0.3
R ₃	0.9	0.7	0.6
S ₁	0.9	0.2	-
S ₂	0.8	0.1	-

where f_u^{in} and f_u^{out} are the molar flowrates of the feed and the product at the inlet and outlet of unit u , respectively; c_u is the cost of unit u ; and ξ_u , μ_u and $\nu_u < 1$ are strictly positive constants. The values of the constants ξ , μ and ν for each of the process units are given in Table 3.

The objective to be maximized is the net cost which is given by $C_2 f_F + \sum_{u \in \mathcal{T}} c_u - C_1 f_P$, where C_1 and C_2 are suitable constants. Note that constraints (63) are not differentiable for the reactors R₁, R₂ and R₃ when the reactor feed has a zero flowrate.

The superstructure optimization problem is given as: *Select between one and three reactors and a separator, if required, such that the net cost is minimized and the problem constraints are satisfied, given the models that describe the process units.*

4.2.2 MSON representation of the superstructure

The superstructure as represented using the MSON framework is shown in Figure 8. The feed to the flowsheet is modelled via a source-unit followed by a splitter. Similarly, the product from the flowsheet is modelled as a sink unit that is preceded by a mixer. We define $\mathcal{F} = \{Source\}$, $\mathcal{P} = \{Sink\}$ and $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{T} \cup \mathcal{F} \cup \mathcal{P}$. Each conditional process unit $u \in \mathcal{T}$, has an associated binary variable z_u . Since exactly one separator is selected if and only if reactor R₃ is chosen and no separator is selected otherwise, we introduce the logical constraint:

$$z_{R_3} = z_{S_1} + z_{S_2} \quad (64)$$

Each process unit in \mathcal{T} has one inlet and one outlet. At each of these inlets and

Figure 8: MSON representation of the flowsheet synthesis problem in case study 2

outlets we replace the mixer and the splitter with a modified mixer and a modified splitter, respectively. We set $f^A = 0.5$ for all modified mixers. For each process unit $u \in \mathcal{T}$, the set \mathcal{C}_u indexes the cost c_u and the set \mathcal{A}_u is empty. We introduce new variables $c_u^S, u \in \mathcal{T}$ and constraints such that $c_u^S = c_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{T}$ if and only if $z_u = 1$. We rewrite the objective function as $C_2 f_F + \sum_{u \in \mathcal{T}} c_u^S - C_1 f_P$. Note that the process unit constraints themselves are unchanged.

4.2.3 Results of case study 2

The reactor-separator network synthesis problem is implemented using the SO-PS algorithm shown in Section 3.5. The progress of the SO-PS algorithm is shown in Table 4. Note that due to the inherent non-convexity of the problem the solution of the master problem, which is a lower bound on the MINLP solution when all the primal problem is convex, is found to be larger than the upper bound in most iterations.

In the initialization phase of the SO-PS algorithm, two primal problems are solved: iteration 1 in which all units except S_2 are selected and iteration 2 in which all units except S_1 are selected. Across the two initialization iterations, all units $u \in \mathcal{T}$ are selected at least once. The two iterations are thus sufficient to initialize the master problem while satisfying constraint (64). A total of 11 flowsheet configurations are feasible with respect to Equation (64) in this reactor-separator network. The optimal flowsheet is identified in

Table 4: Progress of the OA/ER/AP algorithm for the reactor-separator network of case study 2. k is the iteration number, z_u is the value of the binary variable that corresponds to unit $u \in \mathcal{T}$ during iteration k . $F^{(k)}$ is the optimal value of the objective function at the solution of the k^{th} primal problem. BUB is the best (lowest) primal objective function value up to iteration k . $MPS^{(k)}$ is the master problem solution (objective function value) at iteration k .

k	z_{R_1}	z_{R_2}	z_{R_3}	z_{S_1}	z_{S_2}	$F^{(k)}$	BUB	$MPS^{(k)}$
1	1	1	1	1	0	1.3	1.3	-1e6
2	1	1	1	0	1	1.2	1.2	1.3
3	0	1	1	1	0	0.9	0.9	1.8
4	1	0	0	0	0	0.5	0.5	2.7
5	1	1	0	0	0	0.6	0.5	2.8
6	1	0	1	0	1	1.0	0.5	3.4
7	0	1	0	0	0	0.3	0.3	3.9
8	1	0	1	1	0	0.8	0.3	4.5

the seventh iteration of the SO-PS algorithm and corresponds to the best solution reported in Trespalacios and Grossmann (2014) and Burre et al. (2023). The algorithm takes a total of 8 primal problems to terminate as per the stopping criteria in Section 3.5. The optimal flowsheet in which only reactor R_2 is selected has a 77% lower cost than the initial flowsheet tested in iteration 1. The deselection of units S_1 and S_2 does not result in singularities. Thus, in this case, the modified mixers and splitters associated with the inlets and outlets of the two separators may be replaced by regular mixers and splitters.

5 Case study 3 – Column synthesis

The third case study is concerned with the design of a counter-current gas-liquid absorption column to separate a binary mixture. It can be stated as follows:

Given a binary mixture of carbon dioxide and methane with flowrate f_F and mass fraction vector \mathbf{x}_F at pressure P and temperature T_F , and a solvent, find the number of stages N and solvent flowrate that minimize the total annualized cost of separation such that the column has at most \bar{N} equilibrium-stages; the vapour (product) flowrate at the top of the column is at least f_p and the mass fraction of methane in the product is at least \bar{x}_p .

We assume that the pressure P is constant throughout the column. We also assume that the column is perfectly insulated.

5.1 A MSON Superstructure for a counter column

Here we propose a superstructure representation of a column section that may also be applied to the synthesis of extraction columns and extended to the synthesis of distillation columns (Barttfeld et al., 2003, Sargent and Gaminibandara, 1976). The superstructure has the following permanent process units: a vapour source F^V , a liquid source F^L , a vapour sink P^V and a liquid sink P^L .

The selection of stages in the column is represented by an R-graph (Farkas et al., 2008). The column is divided into $|\mathcal{R}|$ subsections where $|\mathcal{R}| = \text{ceil}(\log_2(\bar{N} + 1))$ and $\text{ceil}(x)$ returns the smallest integer greater than or equal to $x \in \mathbb{R}$. Each subsection $u \in \mathcal{R}$, where $\mathcal{R} = \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{R}|\}$, is a conditional unit in our column superstructure, with 2^{u-1} equilibrium stages in which the liquid and vapour streams are contacted in a counter-current fashion. For example, in Figure 9, the column has at most $\bar{N} = 15$ stages. It may be represented by 4 conditional units R_1, R_2, R_3 and R_4 which have 1, 2 and 4 and 8 stages, respectively. A binary variable z_u is used to denote the existence of conditional unit / section u .

To ensure that at least one subsection is selected, we impose the constraint:

$$\sum_{u \in \mathcal{R}} z_u \geq 1. \quad (65)$$

The optimal number of stages $N = \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} 2^{r-1} z_r$ and $N \in \{1, \dots, \bar{N}\}$. Constraint (66) ensures that at most \bar{N} stages are selected:

$$\sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} 2^{r-1} z_r \leq \bar{N}. \quad (66)$$

The total set of units (including the permanent units and conditional units) is given by $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{R} \cup \{F^L, F^V, P^L, P^V\}$. Mixers and splitters connect the units in \mathcal{U} . Inlet and outlet

Figure 9: Elements of the absorption column superstructure that include the inlets and outlets of the sources F^V , F^L , sinks P^V , P^L , and column sections R_1 , R_2 , R_3 , R_4 . R_1 , R_2 , R_3 , and R_4 have 1, 2, 4 and 8 stages, respectively. The mixers and splitters are not shown due to lack of space.

Figure 10: Examples of subsections associated with different units in case study 3. (a) Schematic of subsection around F^V . The vapour splitter allows the vapour feed to flow into units R_1 , R_2 , R_3 and R_4 . (b) Schematic of subsection around P^V . The vapour mixer allows the vapour streams that leave units R_1 , R_2 , R_3 and R_4 to flow into the vapour sink. (c) Schematic of subsection around R_3 . The modified vapour mixer allows mass flows into R_3 from units R_4 and F^V . The modified vapour splitter allows the vapour stream that leaves R_3 to flow into units R_1 , R_2 and P^V . The modified liquid mixer allows flow into R_3 from R_1 , R_2 and F^L . The modified liquid splitter allows the liquid stream that leaves R_3 to flow into R_4 and P^L .

streams and connectivity constraints are defined such that vapour and liquid streams are contacted in a counter-current fashion. As can be seen in Figure 9, source F^L has one liquid outlet β_0^L and one liquid inlet α_0^L , wherein solvent enters the column superstructure. F^L is located at the top of the column superstructure alongside the vapour sink P^V . P^V has one vapour inlet α_0^V and one vapour outlet β_0^V . Similarly, F^V has one vapour outlet $\beta_{|\mathcal{R}|+1}^V$ and one vapour inlet $\alpha_{|\mathcal{R}|+1}^V$ and is located at the bottom of the column superstructure alongside the liquid sink P^L . P^L has one liquid inlet $\alpha_{|\mathcal{R}|+1}^L$ and one liquid outlet $\beta_{|\mathcal{R}|+1}^L$.

Further, as shown in Figure 9, we arrange column subsections $u \in \mathcal{R}$ top-down with subsection R_1 placed directly below P^V and F^L and units arranged in ascending order from top to bottom. Each subsection $u \in \mathcal{R}$ has one liquid inlet at the top of the subsection α_u^L , one vapour inlet α_u^V at the bottom of the subsection, one liquid outlet β_u^L at the bottom of the subsection and one vapour outlet β_u^V at the top of the subsection.

Let set $\mathcal{J} = \{0\} \cup \mathcal{R}$ and $\mathcal{K} = \mathcal{R} \cup \{|\mathcal{R}| + 1\}$. Either a mixer m_i^V or a modified mixer \tilde{m}_i^V is placed at each vapour inlet $\alpha_i^V, \forall i \in \mathcal{J}$. Either a mixer m_i^L or a modified mixer \tilde{m}_i^L is placed at each liquid inlet, $\alpha_i^L, \forall i \in \mathcal{K}$. A modified mixer is used when the inlet is associated with a conditional subsection and a standard mixer is used otherwise. A splitter, which may be either modified or standard, s_o^V (\tilde{s}_o^V) is introduced after each vapour outlet $\beta_o^V, \forall o \in \mathcal{K}$ and a splitter, which is either modified or standard, s_o^L (\tilde{s}_o^L) at each liquid outlet, $\beta_o^L, \forall o \in \mathcal{J}$. As before, modified splitters are placed at the outlets of the conditional subsections and standard splitters are used at the outlets of the permanent units. Figure 10 shows the mixers and splitters associated with example units F^V, P^V and R_3 .

The vapour mixer, which may be either modified or standard, m_i^V (\tilde{m}_i^V), $i \in \mathcal{J}$ allows the mixing of vapour streams that flow from outlets $\beta_o^V, \forall o \in \mathcal{M}_i^V$, where $\mathcal{M}_i^V = \{i + 1, \dots, |\mathcal{R}| + 1\}$, i.e., the vapour mixer m_i^V (\tilde{m}_i^V) allows mixing of vapour streams that exit units located below unit i in the column superstructure. For example, for the column shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10, the modified mixer \tilde{m}_3^V that corresponds to unit R_3 is fed by streams that connect outlets $\beta_o^V, \forall o \in \mathcal{M}_1^V = \{4, 5\}$ with \tilde{m}_3^V . Thus, \tilde{m}_3^V allows the mixing of the vapour streams that exit R_4 and F^V via splitters \tilde{s}_4^V and s_5^V , respectively.

The vapour stream flowing into the mixer at vapour inlet $\alpha_i^V, i \in \mathcal{J}$, from the splitter at vapour outlet $\beta_o^V \in \mathcal{M}_i^V$, has flowrate, temperature and composition denoted by $f_{o,i}^V, T_{o,i}^V$ and $\mathbf{q}_{o,i}^V$, respectively.

The liquid streams are treated in a similar fashion. Liquid inlet stream $\alpha_i^L, i \in \mathcal{K}$ is the output of mixer (or modified mixer) m_i^L (or \tilde{m}_i^L), which allows mixing of streams that flow from splitters at outlets $\beta_o, \forall o \in \mathcal{M}_i^L = \{0, \dots, i-1\}$. That is, each liquid inlet may be connected via mixers and splitters to the liquid outlets of the units that are located above it in the column. For example, for the column shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10, the mixer \tilde{m}_3^L that corresponds to unit R_3 is fed by streams that connect $\beta_o^L, \forall o \in \mathcal{M}_3^L = \{0, 1, 2\}$ to the mixer. Thus the modified mixer \tilde{m}_3^L allows the mixing of the liquid streams that exit F^L, R_1 , and R_2 . The liquid stream flowing into liquid mixer at inlet $\alpha_i^L, i \in \mathcal{K}$ from the splitter at outlet $\beta_o^L \in \mathcal{M}_i^L$, has flowrate, temperature and composition denoted by $f_{o,i}^L, T_{o,i}^L$ and $\mathbf{q}_{o,i}^L$, respectively.

For convenience of notation, we also define sets \mathcal{S}_o^L and \mathcal{S}_o^V . Each splitter at liquid outlet β_o^L in \mathcal{J} is allowed to be connected to the mixer at inlet $\alpha_i^L, i \in \mathcal{S}_o^L$, where $\mathcal{S}_o^L = \{o+1, \dots, |\mathcal{R}|+1\}$. Each splitter at vapour outlet $\beta_o^V, o \in \mathcal{K}$, may be connected to the set of vapour inlets \mathcal{S}_o^V (via mixers), where $\mathcal{S}_o^V = \{0, \dots, o-1\}$.

5.1.1 Flow-validity constraints

We reiterate that when $i \in \mathcal{R}$, the modified mixers and splitters ($\tilde{m}_i^V, \tilde{m}_i^L, \tilde{s}_i^V, \tilde{s}_i^L$) all correspond to conditional column subsection i .

The usual flow validity constraints (7) are added to prevent flows to deselected conditional subsections. Additional flow-validity constraints are needed for this case study as we disallow both partial and total bypassing of stages (and column subsections) as well as side streams. Thus, vapour streams in a simple column flow upwards. To prevent bypassing, constraint (67) imposes that the vapour stream that leaves a unit o is allowed to enter the unit $i, i+1 < o$, only if all the intermediate subsections $k \in \{o-1, \dots, i+1\}$ have the associated binary variable $z_k = 0$. Define $\mathcal{K}_{o,i}^V = \{k | k \in \mathcal{M}_i^V \wedge k < o\}$, i.e., $\mathcal{K}_{o,i}^V$ is the set

of conditional subsections between unit o and unit i . Then,

$$f_{o,i}^V \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_k), \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_{o,i}^V, \forall o \in \mathcal{M}_i^V, \forall i \in \mathcal{R} \quad (67)$$

To illustrate the use of constraint (67), let us consider unit R_1 in Figure 9. Any splitter at outlet β_o^V where $o \in \mathcal{M}_1^V = \{2, 3, 4, 5\}$ may be connected to α_1^V . When $o = 2$, $\mathcal{K}_{2,1}^V = \emptyset$ and thus no constraint is added. When $o = 3$, $\mathcal{K}_{3,1}^V = \{2\}$ yielding

$$f_{3,1}^V \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_2). \quad (68)$$

When $o = 4$, $\mathcal{K}_{4,1}^V = \{2, 3\}$ yielding

$$f_{4,1}^V \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_2) \quad (69)$$

$$f_{4,1}^V \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_3). \quad (70)$$

When $o = 5$, $\mathcal{K}_{5,1}^V = \{2, 3, 4\}$ yielding

$$f_{5,1}^V \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_2) \quad (71)$$

$$f_{5,1}^V \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_3) \quad (72)$$

$$f_{5,1}^V \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_4). \quad (73)$$

Analogously, the liquid stream must flow downwards through all selected units. To ensure this, we impose that a liquid that leaves a splitter at outlet β_o^L can enter a mixer at inlet α_i^L , where $i > o + 1$ only if all intermediate units k are deselected, that is, where $z_k = 0, \forall k \in \{o + 1, \dots, i - 1\}$. We define $\mathcal{K}_{o,i}^L = \{k | k \in \mathcal{M}_i^L \wedge k > o\}$, i.e., $\mathcal{K}_{o,i}^L$ is the set of intermediate conditional subsections between unit o and unit i .

$$f_{o,i}^L \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_k) \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_{o,i}^L, \forall o \in \mathcal{M}_i^L, \forall i \in \mathcal{R}. \quad (74)$$

To illustrate the use of constraint (74), let us consider unit R_3 in Figure 9 for which

$\mathcal{M}_3^L = \{0, 1, 2\}$. We obtain the following system of inequalities:

$$f_{0,3}^L \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_1) \quad (75)$$

$$f_{0,3}^L \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_2) \quad (76)$$

$$f_{1,3}^L \leq \bar{f}(1 - z_2) \quad (77)$$

5.1.2 Process-level model for each subsection

Each stage is modelled as an equilibrium stage via MESH equations. The SAFT- γ Mie (Papaioannou et al., 2014) equation of state is used to calculate all the required thermodynamic properties using the parameters reported in (Burger et al., 2013). We note that more detailed models that account for mass and heat transfer resistances may also be used without changing the superstructure.

For each subsection $u \in \mathcal{R}$, we compute total values for the liquid mass density, the vapour mass density and the volumetric vapour flowrate over all stages in the subsection. These are denoted by $\tilde{\rho}_u^L$, $\tilde{\rho}_u^V$, and \tilde{v}_u^V , respectively and are given by

$$\tilde{\rho}_u^L = \sum_{j=1}^{2^{u-1}} \rho_{u,j}^L \quad (78)$$

$$\tilde{\rho}_u^V = \sum_{j=1}^{2^{u-1}} \rho_{u,j}^V \quad (79)$$

$$\tilde{v}_u^V = \sum_{j=1}^{2^{u-1}} v_{u,j}^V \quad (80)$$

where $\rho_{u,j}^L$ is the mass density of the liquid leaving stage j in section u (in kg/m^3), $\rho_{u,j}^V$ is the mass density of the vapour leaving stage j in section u (in kg/m^3) and $v_{u,j}^V$ is the volumetric flowrate of the vapour leaving stage j in section u (in m^3/s). The total quantities are referred to as output variables and are indexed by set \mathcal{C}_u . They are used in flowsheet-level column sizing constraints by defining the following new flowsheet-level

variables: $\tilde{\rho}_u^{L,S}, \tilde{\rho}_u^{V,S}$ and $\tilde{v}_u^{V,S}$.

$$\tilde{\rho}_u^{L,S} = \tilde{\rho}_u^L; \quad \tilde{\rho}_u^{V,S} = \tilde{\rho}_u^V; \quad \tilde{v}_u^{V,S} = \tilde{v}_u^V. \quad (81)$$

5.1.3 Flowsheet-level constraints

The flooding velocity u^{flood} (in m/s) and the diameter D (in m) and height H (in m) of the column are computed using correlations in Sinnott and Towler (2020a) and depend on i) $\hat{\rho}^L$ and $\hat{\rho}^V$, the average of the liquid densities and of the vapour densities, respectively, across all the stages that are selected to be in the column and ii) \hat{v}^V , the average of the vapour volumes across all selected stages. These quantities are functions of the modified output variables $\tilde{\rho}_u^{L,S}$, $\tilde{\rho}_u^{V,S}$ and $\tilde{v}_u^{V,S}$ and are computed using

$$N = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{R}} 2^{u-1} z_u \quad (82)$$

$$\hat{\rho}^L = \frac{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{R}} \tilde{\rho}_u^{L,S}}{N} \quad (83)$$

$$\hat{\rho}^V = \frac{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{R}} \tilde{\rho}_u^{V,S}}{N} \quad (84)$$

$$\hat{v}^V = \frac{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{R}} \tilde{v}_u^{V,S}}{N} \quad (85)$$

$$u^{\text{flood}} = (-0.171lt^2 + 0.27lt - 0.047) \sqrt{\frac{\hat{\rho}^L - \hat{\rho}^V}{\hat{\rho}^V}} \quad (86)$$

$$D = \sqrt{\frac{4\hat{v}^V}{\pi u^{\text{flood}}}} \quad (87)$$

$$H = 1.15 \frac{lt}{E} N \quad (88)$$

where lt is the tray spacing (in m) and E the stage efficiency factor.

We assume that the solvent is fully recovered by an ideal regeneration step whose cost is not considered in this study. We use the costing correlations given in Pereira et al. (2011) to compute the total capital investment TCI and the annual column operating expenses TOC of the absorption column. Lastly, the objective function is taken to be the total

annualized cost of the absorber, TAC and is computed as

$$TAC = TOC + \eta TCI \quad (89)$$

where η is the annual capital charge ratio.

Other flowsheet-level constraints include minimum requirements imposed on the purity and the flowrate of the product stream that exits the vapour sink.

5.2 Implementation and Initialization

The hybrid framework given in Section 3.5 is used to solve the problem. As before, we implement all constraints in the PS environment and the SO-PS algorithm is used to solve the problem. To initialize the master problem we simply set the binary variables corresponding to all column subsections to one. We set both the initial step length and the maximum step length parameters of the SRQPD solver in gPROMS to 0.1.

Initialization of the highly-coupled counter column model can often be a challenge in PS and MO environments. We find that the modified mixers and splitters provide a simple route to initialization of the process unit-level constraints. We first decouple column subsections by using the initialization procedure in section 3.6. We set flowrates of the fictitious streams in the liquid and vapour mixers and their intensive properties equal to that of a liquid and a vapour that are in equilibrium with each other, in accordance with the column initialization procedure given in Keskes (2007). It follows that in this case, the liquid (vapour) streams at the outlet of each stage and each column subsection are identical to the streams at the inlets. Thus, a feasible solution to the MESH equations of each equilibrium stage as well as each column subsection in the column superstructure may easily be determined. The generated solution is then be used to initialize a simple counter-current column with strictly positive flows between the process units.

Table 5: Results for case study 3, column synthesis for CO₂ removal from methane. The number of stages, N , solvent flowrate f , total annualized cost TAC , total capital investment TCI and operating expenses $OPEX$ are reported. The first row shows the best solution returned by the SO-PS algorithm. The second row shows the design when the number of stages is fixed to 15 and the third row when it is fixed to 5

Case	N	f (kmol/s)	$TAC(10^6\text{USD})$	$TCI(10^6\text{USD})$	$OPEX(10^6\text{USD})$
Best found	6	0.64	0.59	1.37	0.32
Fixed-15	15	0.60	1.04	3.01	0.44
Fixed-5	5	0.65	0.53	1.17	0.30

5.3 Results

We show results for the separation of carbon-dioxide and methane for a feed flowrate of 1 kmol/s at 7.5 MPa, 298 K and 20% CO₂. The pure solvent tetra(oxymethylene)dimethylether (CH₃O(CH₂O)₄CH₃), which has been identified to be a promising solvent for the separation of this mixture in other studies (Burger et al., 2015, Gopinath et al., 2016), enters the column at 7.5 MPa and 298 K and flowrate f . We find the optimal number of stages N and solvent flowrate f that minimize the total annualized cost TAC when \bar{N} is 15, f_p is 0.66, x_p is 0.97, E is 0.8, lt is 0.6m and η is 0.199, corresponding to a 15% cost of capital and plant life of 10 years (Sinnott and Towler, 2020b).

The SO-PS algorithm takes a total of 8 iterations to satisfy the stopping criterion. The optimal column design found by the algorithm corresponds to a column with six stages out of the possible 15 stages. Across the 8 iterations, The SO-PS algorithm identifies 5 feasible columns. We also obtain the minimum TAC for a column in which the number of stages is fixed at 15, which is 76% higher than the 6-stage column column (see Table 5). The TCI of the 15-stage column is 120% higher than the best column identified by SO-PS, highlighting the large effect of column synthesis on the capital costs of separation columns. The solvent usage in the optimal column is almost the same as the fixed column. In both columns the constraint that the product flowrate is at least f_p is active. Note that to mitigate the effects of non-convexity, we used a linear constraint on product flowrate here instead of the bilinear constraint on product recovery that is commonly used in the literature.

Due to the inherent nonconvexity of the problem, the SO-PS algorithm is not guaran-

teed to yield a global minimum. To validate our results, we enumerate all integer choices the number of stages in the column and solve the resulting NLPs. We find that a column with 5 stages has the smallest TAC , as shown in Table 5. The fixed-5 column has a TAC that is 10% less than best solution identified by SO-PS. We also find that all columns with fewer than 5 stages are infeasible. In contrast to full enumeration, the SO-PS algorithm evaluates only 53% of the search space to arrive at a solution. While the SO-PS algorithm converges to a local minimum, it returns a high-quality solution which is the nearest alternative to what appears to be the globally-optimal column.

6 Conclusion

The optimization of a given superstructure may be cast as an MINLP using several alternative and mathematically-equivalent problem formulations (Trespacios and Grossmann, 2014). However, the choice of MINLP formulation affects the performance of MINLP optimization in practice (Trespacios and Grossmann, 2014). A novel problem formulation with favourable numerical properties, the modified state-operator network (MSON), has been presented in this study. It is based on based on an exact reformulation of mixers and splitters and the introduction of fictitious streams.

The MSON is a general framework that may be used to solve a wide range of flowsheet design problems and is suitable for use with rigorous process models. The MSON formulation requires the introduction of mixers, splitters and streams, as well as new variables, but does not entail any modifications of models used for process units. It has been presented within the context of a big-M formulation, although other approaches can be followed. We have illustrated the methodology with the synthesis of a toy flowsheet to highlight the challenges that can arise in superstructure optimization. The numerical performance of the MSON as well as other standard problem formulations were benchmarked for the toy problem across a range of optimization solvers and two platforms: gPROMS and GAMS. The MSON was found to be robust and to avoid any singularities, outperforming all other problem formulations even on a simple problem.

The MSON formalism was further tested on a reactor-separator superstructure from the literature and on a novel superstructure for the synthesis of a counter-current separation column, a challenging problem in superstructure optimization. The use of the MSON for these problems has been found to have several practical implications. Numerical singularities due to zero flows are completely averted. The column synthesis, in particular, has been carried out on the basis of high-fidelity rigorous models with detailed thermodynamics, that is, an advanced equation of state. As a by-product, the MSON also offers a systematic framework for initialization of a counter-current column model thus, averting labour-intensive process initialization by trial and error. Similarly, the MSON also offers a systematic framework for the initialization of complex flowsheets and trains of separation columns.

As high-dimensional MINLPs are prone to non-convergence, the robust framework presented here for superstructure optimization is appealing. Across case studies with varying degrees of complexity the modifications to the flowsheet-level constraints was limited and process unit-level constraints remained unaltered. The MSON is a promising approach for the synthesis of complex flowsheets. The extension of the MSON to flowsheets in which the pressure is variable will be studied next.

7 Acknowledgements

The authors thank Terrence Crombie, Senior Computing Officer, Imperial College London, for his valuable inputs on interfacing gPROMS with C++.

References

ARKI Consulting & Development A/S (2024a). CONOPT.

ARKI Consulting & Development A/S (2024b). SBB.

AspenTech (2015). Aspen Plus.

- Barttfeld, M., Aguirre, P. A., and Grossmann, I. E. (2003). Alternative representations and formulations for the economic optimization of multicomponent distillation columns. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 27:363–383.
- Bowskill, D. H., Tropp, U. E., Gopinath, S., Jackson, G., Galindo, A., and Adjiman, C. S. (2020). Beyond a heuristic analysis: integration of process and working-fluid design for organic rankine cycles. *Mol. Syst. Des. Eng.*, 5:493–510.
- Bugosen, S., Laird, C., and Parker, R. (2023). Chemical process flowsheet optimization with full space, surrogate, and implicit formulations of a gibbs reactor.
- Burger, J., Papaioannou, V., Galindo, A., Jackson, G., and Adjiman, C. S. (2013). Integrated process and solvent design of physical CO₂ absorption using the SAFT $-\gamma$ Mie equation of state and hierarchical optimisation. *AIChE annual meeting, San Francisco, USA*.
- Burger, J., Papaioannou, V., Gopinath, S., Jackson, G., Galindo, A., and Adjiman, C. S. (2015). A hierarchical method to integrated solvent and process design of physical CO₂ absorption using the SAFT- γ Mie approach. *AIChE Journal*, 61:3249–3269.
- Burre, J., Bongartz, D., and Mitsos, A. (2023). Comparison of minlp formulations for global superstructure optimization. *Optim Eng*, 24:801–830.
- Bynum, M. L., Hackebeil, G. A., Hart, W. E., Laird, C. D., Nicholson, B. L., Siirola, J. D., Watson, J.-P., and Woodruff, D. L. (2021). *Pyomo Overview*, pages 25–36. Springer International Publishing, Cham.
- Byrd, R. H., Nocedal, J., and Waltz, R. A. (2006). *Knitro: An Integrated Package for Nonlinear Optimization*, pages 35–59. Springer US, Boston, MA.
- Caballero, J. (2015). Logic hybrid simulation-optimization algorithm for distillation design. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 72:284 – 299. A Tribute to Ignacio E. Grossmann.

- Caballero, J. A., Milán-Yañez, D., and Grossmann, I. E. (2005). Optimal synthesis of distillation columns: Integration of process simulators in a disjunctive programming environment. *Computer Aided Chemical Engineering*, 20:715 – 720.
- Cavalcanti, S. M. and Barton, P. I. (2020). Multiple steady states and nonsmooth bifurcations in dry and vaporless distillation columns. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 59(40):18000–18018.
- Douglas, J. M. (1985). A hierarchical decision procedure for process synthesis. *AIChE Journal*, 31(3):353–362.
- Dowling, A. W. (2018). *An Equation-based Framework for Large-Scale Flowsheet Optimization and Applications for Oxycombustion Power System Design*. PhD thesis, Carnegie Mellon University.
- Dowling, A. W. and Biegler, L. T. (2015a). *Degeneracy Hunter: An Algorithm for Determining Irreducible Sets of Degenerate Constraints in Mathematical Programs*, page 809–814. Elsevier.
- Dowling, A. W. and Biegler, L. T. (2015b). A framework for efficient large scale equation-oriented flowsheet optimization. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 72:3 – 20. A Tribute to Ignacio E. Grossmann.
- Farkas, T., Czuczai, B., Rev, E., and Lelkes, Z. (2008). New minlp model and modified outer approximation algorithm for distillation column synthesis. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 47(9):3088–3103.
- FICO (2024). Xpress optimization.
- Fourer, R., Gay, D. M., and Kernighan, B. W. (1989). Ampl: A mathematical programming language. In Wallace, S. W., editor, *Algorithms and Model Formulations in Mathematical Programming*, pages 150–151, Berlin, Heidelberg. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

- GAMS Development Corporation (2024). General Algebraic Modeling System (GAMS) release 36.1.0, fairfax, va, usa, 2021.
- Gill, P. E., Murray, W., and Saunders, M. A. (2005). Snopt: An sqp algorithm for large-scale constrained optimization. *SIAM Rev.*, 47(1):99–131.
- Glover, F. (1975). Improved linear integer programming formulations of nonlinear integer problems. *Management Science*, 22(4):455–460.
- Gopinath, S., Jackson, G., Galindo, A., and Adjiman, C. S. (2016). Outer approximation algorithm with physical domain reduction for computer-aided molecular and separation process design. *AIChE Journal*, 62(9):3484–3504.
- Gurobi Optimization, Inc. (2024). Gurobi optimizer reference manual.
- Javaloyes-Antón, J., Kronqvist, J., and Caballero, J. A. (2022). Simulation-based optimization of distillation processes using an extended cutting plane algorithm. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 159:107655.
- Keskes, E. (2007). *Integrated process and solvent design for CO₂ removal from natural gas*. PhD thesis, Imperial College London.
- Kocis, G. and Grossmann, I. (1989). Computational experience with dicopt solving minlp problems in process systems engineering. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 13(3):307–315.
- Kocis, G. R. and Grossmann, I. E. (1987). Relaxation strategy for the structural optimization of process flow sheets. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 26(9):1869–1880.
- Kondili, E., Pantelides, C., and Sargent, R. (1993). A general algorithm for short-term scheduling of batch operations—i. milp formulation. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 17(2):211–227. An International Journal of Computer Applications in Chemical Engineering.

- Kossack, S., Kraemer, K., and Marquardt, W. (2006). Efficient optimization-based design of distillation columns for homogenous azeotropic mixtures. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 45(25):8492–8502.
- Kronqvist, J., Lundell, A., and Westerlund, T. (2015). The extended supporting hyperplane algorithm for convex mixed-integer nonlinear programming. *Journal of Global Optimization*, 64(2):249–272.
- Lastusilta, T., Bussieck, M. R., and Westerlund, T. (2009). An experimental study of the gams/alphaecp minlp solver. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 48(15):7337–7345.
- Lee, S. and Grossmann, I. E. (2003). Global optimization of nonlinear generalized disjunctive programming with bilinear equality constraints: applications to process networks. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 27(11):1557–1575.
- Lee, U., Mitsos, A., and Han, C. (2016). Optimal retrofit of a {CO₂} capture pilot plant using superstructure and rate-based models. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 50:57 – 69.
- Liñán, D. A., Bernal, D. E., Ricardez-Sandoval, L. A., and Gómez, J. M. (2020). Optimal design of superstructures for placing units and streams with multiple and ordered available locations. part i: A new mathematical framework. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 137:106794.
- McBride, K. and Sundmacher, K. (2019). Overview of surrogate modeling in chemical process engineering. *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, 91(3):228–239.
- Mencarelli, L., Chen, Q., Pagot, A., and Grossmann, I. E. (2020). A review on superstructure optimization approaches in process system engineering. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 136:106808.
- Murtagh, B. A., Saunders, M. A., Murray, W., Gill, P. E., Raman, R., and Kalvelagen, E. (2002). Minos: A solver for large-scale nonlinear optimization problems.

- Navarro-Amorós, M. A., Ruiz-Femenia, R., and Caballero, J. A. (2014). Integration of modular process simulators under the generalized disjunctive programming framework for the structural flowsheet optimization. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 67(Supplement C):13 – 25.
- Papaioannou, V., Lafitte, T., Avendaño, C., Adjiman, C. S., Jackson, G., Müller, E. A., and Galindo, A. (2014). Group contribution methodology based on the statistical associating fluid theory for heteronuclear molecules formed from Mie segments. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 140(5).
- Pereira, F. E., Keskes, E., Galindo, A., Jackson, G., and Adjiman, C. S. (2011). Integrated solvent and process design using a SAFT-VR thermodynamic description: High-pressure separation of carbon dioxide and methane. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 35:474–491.
- Raghunathan, A. U. and Biegler, L. T. (2003). Mathematical programs with equilibrium constraints (mpecs) in process engineering. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 27(10):1381 – 1392.
- Raman, R. and Grossmann, I. (1994). Modelling and computational techniques for logic based integer programming. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 18(7):563 – 578. An International Journal of Computer Applications in Chemical Engineering.
- Sargent, R. and Gaminibandara, K. (1976). Optimum design of plate distillation columns. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 19:83 – 88.
- Siemens (1996-2024). gPROMS.
- Sinnott, R. and Towler, G. (2020a). Chapter 11 - separation columns (distillation, absorption and extraction). In Sinnott, R. and Towler, G., editors, *Chemical Engineering Design (Sixth Edition)*, Chemical Engineering Series, pages 645–772. Butterworth-Heinemann, sixth edition edition.

- Sinnott, R. and Towler, G. (2020b). Chapter 6 - costing and project evaluation. In Sinnott, R. and Towler, G., editors, *Chemical Engineering Design (Sixth Edition)*, Chemical Engineering Series, pages 275–369. Butterworth-Heinemann, sixth edition edition.
- Skiborowski, M., Harwardt, A., and Marquardt, W. (2015). Efficient optimization-based design for the separation of heterogeneous azeotropic mixtures. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 72:34–51. A Tribute to Ignacio E. Grossmann.
- Smith, E. (1996). *On the Optimal Design of Continuous Processes*. Imperial College London.
- Smith, E. and Pantelides, C. (1995). Design of reaction/separation networks using detailed models. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 19:83 – 88.
- Trespalacios, F. and Grossmann, I. (2014). Review of mixed-integer nonlinear and generalized disjunctive programming methods. *Chemie-Ingenieur-Technik*, 86(7):991–1012.
- Trespalacios, F. and Grossmann, I. E. (2015). Improved big-m reformulation for generalized disjunctive programs. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 76:98–103.
- Tula, A. K., Eden, M. R., and Gani, R. (2015). Process synthesis, design and analysis using a process-group contribution method. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 81:245–259. Special Issue: Selected papers from the 8th International Symposium on the Foundations of Computer-Aided Process Design (FOCAPD 2014), July 13-17, 2014, Cle Elum, Washington, USA.
- Türkay, M. and Grossmann, I. E. (1996). Logic-based minlp algorithms for the optimal synthesis of process networks. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 20(8):959 – 978.
- Viswanathan, J. and Grossmann, I. (1990). A combined penalty function and outer-approximation method for {MINLP} optimization. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 14(7):769 – 782.

- Vollmer, N., Al, R., Gernaey, K. V., and Sin, G. (2021). Synergistic optimization framework for the process synthesis and design of biorefineries. *Frontiers of Chemical Science and Engineering*, pages 1 – 23.
- Wu, W., Henao, C. A., and Maravelias, C. T. (2016). A superstructure representation, generation, and modeling framework for chemical process synthesis. *AIChE Journal*, 62(9):3199–3214.
- Wächter, A. and Biegler, L. T. (2005). On the implementation of an interior-point filter line-search algorithm for large-scale nonlinear programming. *Mathematical Programming*, 106(1):25–57.
- Yeomans, H. and Grossmann, I. E. (2000a). Disjunctive programming models for the optimal design of distillation columns and separation sequences. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 39(6):1637–1648.
- Yeomans, H. and Grossmann, I. E. (2000b). Optimal design of complex distillation columns using rigorous tray-by-tray disjunctive programming models. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 39(11):4326–4335.